

Understanding microbiome supra-metabolism responses under strong selective pressures as a resource for designing synthetic gene arrangements encoding key co-selected functions for environmental biotechnology applications

Sonia Marcela Villegas Plazas

A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
Doctor of Engineering at Universidad del Valle, Cali, Colombia

Doctorado en Ingeniería, énfasis Ingeniería Sanitaria y Ambiental
Programa de Postgrado en Ingeniería Sanitaria y Ambiental – PISA
Escuela de Ingeniería de Recursos Naturales y del Ambiente – EIDENAR
Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad del Valle, Cali, Colombia.

Thesis Supervisors:

Dr. Janeth Sanabria

Dr. Howard Junca

2020

Agradecimientos

Todos los que me han acompañado y arropado estos cuatro años y medio hacen parte de esto, a ustedes gracias por caminar conmigo y tenderme la mano siempre.

La ejecución de esta tesis fue posible gracias a las siguientes instituciones: Departamento Administrativo de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación – COLCIENCIAS – por la beca otorgada (727) (Colombia). La Universidad del Valle y el grupo de investigación *Procesos avanzados para Tratamientos Biológicos y Químicos* – GAOX – (Cali, Valle del Cauca). El grupo de investigación *Microbial Ecology: Metabolism, Genomics & Evolution, Div. Ecogenomics & Holobionts* de Microbiomas Foundation (Chía, Colombia). El grupo de investigación *Molecular Environmental Microbiology Laboratory* del Centro Nacional de Biotecnología – CNB, CSIC – (Madrid, España). La *Unidad de Saneamiento y Biotecnología Ambiental* – USBA – de la Pontificia Universidad Javeriana (Bogotá, Colombia).

Table of Contents

1	ABSTRACT / RESUMEN	5
2	INTRODUCTION	7
2.1	Background	7
2.2	References	11
1	CHAPTER I: A composite taxonomical and functional framework of microbiomes under Acid Mine Drainage bioremediation systems	12
1.1	Introduction	13
1.2	Engineering of bioremediation process: an opportunity to improve understanding of community dynamics and functional stability	14
1.3	Integrated omics-perspective for effective bioremediation	15
1.4	Developing a metagenomic view of AMD ecosystems	16
1.4.1	AMD biofilm, water, and impacted environments	19
1.4.2	AMD bioremediation engineering systems	22
1.5	Predicted functional profiles of AMD communities	24
1.6	Conclusions and remarks	25
1.7	References	27
2	CHAPTER II: On acid mine drainage detoxification: highly selected genes in microbiomes of biochemical passive reactors are enriched in two-component regulatory systems and ABC transporters	32
2.1	Introduction	33
2.2	Experimental Procedures	34
2.2.1	Samples source	34
2.2.2	Characterization of the microbial community structure	34
2.2.3	Whole shotgun metagenome sequencing and analyses	34
2.2.3.1	Metagenomic DNA extraction and sequencing	34
2.2.3.2	Metagenome assembly and gene annotation	35
2.2.3.3	Frequency abundance determination of each ORF	35
2.2.3.4	Statistical Analysis	35
2.3	Results and Discussion	36
2.3.1	Determining the structure and composition of microbial communities from BPR	36
2.3.2	Supra-metabolism characterization through metagenomics	39
2.3.3	Carbon metabolism	39
2.3.4	Membrane Transport	41
2.3.5	Oxidative phosphorylation and energy metabolism	41
2.4	Conclusions	42
2.5	References	43
3	CHAPTER III: Evaluation of a promiscuous conjugative plasmid (pMating221) as a plausible gene mobilization tool for genetic bioaugmentation of environmental bacteria	45
3.1	Introduction	46
3.2	Materials and Methods-	47
3.2.1	Plasmid concept and design	47
3.2.2	Bacteria isolation from AMD-impacted soils	47
3.2.3	Evaluation of pMating221-transformation of aerobic isolates	48
3.2.4	Evaluation of pMating221-transformation of anaerobic isolates	48
3.2.5	pMating221 transconjugation experiments	49
3.2.6	Confirmation of transformant colonies and taxonomic identification	49
3.2.7	Design proposals of accessory modules for pMating221 including specific genes for AMD metabolism	49
3.3	Results and Discussion	51
3.4	Conclusions	55
3.5	References	55
1	OUTLOOK	57
1.1	Concluding remarks	57
1.2	References	59
2	APPENDIX	60
2.1	Annex Chapter I	60
2.2	Annex Chapter II	65

Especial List: Tables and Figures

INTRODUCTION

Figure 1. Scheme representing research pathways that guided the formulation of this project	9
--	---

CHAPTER I

Figure 1. Overview of main biochemical processes occurring in AMD bioremediation systems	14
Figure 2. Integration approaches and rationale for conventional and omics-based engineered and synthetic enhancements of bioremediation by environmental microbiomes	17
Figure 3. species richness and alpha diversity of AMD microbiome compiled data and sampled ecosystem types	18
Figure 4. Joint accumulated microbiome composition of reviewed ecosystems under AMD selection	19
Figure 5. Heatmap representing the relative abundance of predominant genera in all microbiomes in ecosystems under AMD selection with data publicly available	22
Figure 6. Bar plot summarizing functional profiles predicted using the R package Tax4Fun	24
Figure 7. Bubble plot representing the KO abundance of 5 sub metabolic pathways that are part of the sulfur metabolism	26

CHAPTER II

Figure 1. A) Species richness and alpha-diversity of all samples, differentiating by treatment time and reactor section. B) Relative frequency of genera with significant differences between treatment time and reactor section. C) Summarizing two-way crossed ANOVA data for genera with p value < 0.01	37
Figure 2. A) Significant taxon co-occurrence revealing three major modules of correlations inside the BPRs microbiomes. B) Distributions of metabolisms previously described for the genera composing each one of the modules	38
Figure 3. Relative abundance of COG in each sample, according the average fold coverage.....	39
Figure 4. Frequency of main reactions in A) cellulose degradation and B) the reductive tricarboxylic acid cycle for each sample, represented in log ₁₀ of the average fold coverage	40
Figure 5. Comparative abundance of genes coding for specific Two-component systems and ABC Transports in each sample, represented in log ₁₀ of the average fold coverage	41
Figure 6. Frequency of each reaction in assimilatory and dissimilatory sulfate reduction for each sample, represented in log ₁₀ of the average fold coverage	42

CHAPTER III

Figure 1. Module architecture of plasmid <i>pMating221</i>	48
Figure 2. Structure of accessory modules designed to introduce them inside <i>pMating221</i> and spread metabolic functions specially related to AMD bioremediation: 2A. Sulfate transport system; 2B. anaerobic sulfite reduction; and 2C. β -Glucosidase activity	51
Figure 3. Distance matrix tree showing phylogenetic positions of isolates classified into three different genera	52
Table 1. Characterization of isolates and the results of the transformation experiments	53
Figure 4. Photographs showing how <i>pMating221</i> acquisition changed the original pigmentation of the colony code 22 (<i>Aeromonas</i> sp.). A. Original pigmentation of the colony; B. Morphology acquired after transformation	54
Table 2. Pairwise of colonies tested in transconjugation experiments	54

OUTLOOK

Figure 1. Bibliometric mapping showing the structure of large-scale research topics in the field of AMD bioremediation	58
---	----

ABSTRACT

Bioremediation encompasses a plethora of technologies and approaches using biologically derived functions to transform contaminants to a non-harmful condition. It is now an essential application to restore the impact of unsustainable human activities impacting global ecosystems. Therefore, research to improve bioremediation strategies and tools are now priorities on environmental sciences. Bioaugmentation, biostimulation, bioreactors, synthetic consortia, and recombinant microorganisms, are some of the most remarkable approaches and components. Improving its efficiency requires a fundamental understanding about how microbial communities resist, thrive and grow under the strong selection that a contaminant is posing in biological systems. Omic technologies are allowing such exploration and discovery with a wider and deeper resolution. Functional metagenomics and sequence-driven screenings are powerful tools for understanding bioremediation processes, allowing the generation of input information for modelling microbiomes dynamics during the adaptation to pollution. This project is presenting one of the most complete comparative assessments of microbial communities in diverse environments under acid mine drainage (AMD) challenge, the major waste generated by the mining industry producing serious impacts on human health and ecosystems. It is also presenting a detailed performed characterization on highly diverse microbiomes at customized reactors operating for AMD bioremediation. By using shotgun metagenomics, it was possible to identify key metabolic functions with increased frequency during effective bioremediation such as those novel gene variants codifying sulfate transport systems, sulfite reduction and cellulose degradation. These genes are suitable targets to design a proposal on genetic bioaugmentation. To this end, a tool for such envisioned environmental gene mobilization in microbiomes by means of a promiscuous conjugative plasmid (*pMating221*) was proposed and tested; and genetic modules for the episomal element *pMating221* were designed as a final part of this work. I demonstrated that it can be transferred by simple transformation into naturally competent aerobic and anaerobic bacterial strains isolated from AMD impacted environments, proving it has broad host range of transformation and potential for conjugative transfer, as an additional foundation for gene augmentation in microbiomes for bioremediation.

RESUMEN

La biorremediación abarca un amplio abanico de tecnologías y enfoques que utilizan funciones derivadas de la biología para transformar los contaminantes a una condición no tóxica. Es una aplicación esencial para restaurar el impacto de las actividades humanas insostenibles que afectan a los ecosistemas mundiales. Por consiguiente, las investigaciones para mejorar las estrategias y herramientas de biorremediación son ahora prioritarias en las ciencias ambientales. Bioaumentación, bioestimulación, biorreactores, consorcios sintéticos y microorganismos recombinantes son algunos de sus enfoques y componentes más notables. Para mejorar su eficacia es necesario comprender a fondo cómo las comunidades microbianas son capaces de resistir, prosperar y crecer bajo un selector fuerte, como actúa un contaminante que impacta en sistemas biológicos. Las tecnologías ómicas están permitiendo tal exploración y descubrimiento con una resolución más amplia y profunda. La metagenómica funcional y las detecciones basadas en secuencia constituyen herramientas poderosas para comprender los procesos de biorremediación, permitiendo la generación de información de entrada para modelar la dinámica de los microbiomas durante la adaptación a la contaminación. Este proyecto presenta una de las evaluaciones comparativas más completas de las comunidades microbianas en diversos ambientes sometidos al impacto de drenaje ácido de minas (DAM), los principales desechos generados por la industria minera que producen graves repercusiones en la salud humana y los ecosistemas. También se presenta una caracterización detallada realizada sobre microbiomas muy diversos en reactores diseñados para lograr la biorremediación de DAM. Mediante la utilización de la secuenciación masiva de metagenomas, fue posible identificar las funciones metabólicas clave con mayor frecuencia durante la biorremediación efectiva, principalmente aquellas nuevas variantes de genes que codifican los sistemas de transporte de sulfatos, la reducción de sulfitos y la degradación de la celulosa. Estos genes son blancos adecuados para diseñar una propuesta de bioaumento genético. Con ese fin, se propuso y evaluó una herramienta para la movilización de los genes ambientales previstos en los microbiomas mediante un plásmido conjugado promiscuo, lo que dio como resultado el diseño de módulos genéticos adicionales para el elemento episomal *pMating221* como parte final de este trabajo. Demostré que puede transferirse por simple transformación en cepas bacterianas aeróbicas y anaeróbicas naturalmente competentes, aisladas de entornos impactados por el DAM, demostrando que tiene una amplia gama de transformación en el huésped y potencial para la transferencia conjugada, pensado como un elemento fundamental inicial para posibles aplicaciones posteriores tales como la modificación genética de microbiomas con genes que favorezcan la acción de agentes biorremediadores.

INTRODUCTION

Rationale, purpose, and approach of this doctoral thesis

Marcela Villegas-Plazas^{1,2}

¹RG Microbial Ecology: Metabolism, Genomics & Evolution, Div. Ecogenomics & Holobionts, Microbiomas Foundation, LT11A, 250008, Chia, Colombia

²Environmental Microbiology and Biotechnology Laboratory, Engineering School of Environmental & Natural Resources, Engineering Faculty, Universidad del Valle, Cali, Colombia

2.1 Background

Since the middle of the last century, biotechnology has emerged as an eco-friendly technology to create different products or transform hazardous wastes by using biological systems. Today, biotechnology covers many different disciplines such as biochemistry, molecular biology, bioinformatics, systems biology, and engineering. Nowadays, it is highly used in industry, agriculture, biomedical sciences and environmental restoration. The environmental biotechnology is the application of different processes to detect, remediate or prevent the emission of pollutants into the environment. Among them, the use of biotechnological techniques with emphasis on bioremediation has currently become a priority for achieving the restoration of a sustainable Earth's state (de Lorenzo et al., 2016).

Bioremediation involves the elimination of hazardous emerging chemicals transforming their chemical structure by the action of the microbial metabolism (Adams et al., 2015). On the last decade, there has been a growing tendency to address these issues from engineering perspectives such as the design and modeling of bioreactors, which has brought several advantages compared to other *in-situ* and *ex-situ* bioremediation techniques (Azubuike et al., 2016). Bioreactors, in all their types, allow increased mass transfer rates through the microorganisms, increase the contact microorganism/pollutant/nutrient and offer the possibility of maintaining excellent control of environmental parameters (Villegas-plazas et al., 2019), which has made them an outstanding alternative to improve bioremediation processes.

The implementation of bioreactors in bioremediation strategies has facilitated the transition between the use of unique strains or defined consortia to the use of adapted microbial communities in the transformation of the same pollutants. This has improved bioremediation due to the broader metabolic flexibility exhibit by microbial communities and their possibility to display division of the catabolic labor (Jagmann and Philipp, 2014). Compare to pure cultures or small defined consortia, those bioreactors with complex microbiomes can perform pollutant conversion with a greater robustness and stability towards environmental perturbations. In this context, the effectiveness of bioremediation relies heavily on a fundamental understanding of how microorganisms are able to grow in highly contaminated sites, and how biological functionalities could be induced in a complex microbial community by the pollution.

The revolutionary improvements in high-throughput DNA sequencing technologies and the generation and development of several new 'omics' research fields, have been fundamental tools to get into the functional

characterization of microbial communities. These data provide compositional snapshots of the species, genes, metabolites and metabolic pathways present in any microbiome (Widder et al., 2016); therefore, the current challenge for microbial ecology is to convert this information into fundamental insights and predictions guiding the improvement of bioprocesses. A key insight to get into this, is the development of theoretical models of taxonomic and metabolic dynamics inside the microbial communities, which requires atemporary analyzes under controlled abiotic conditions, such as those characteristics on bioreactors; this is one of the main reasons why bioreactors are an excellent experimental scenario for 'omics' approaches.

Considering systems biology and microbial ecology for the engineering of bioreactors relying on complex microbial communities, allows improvements in process design, monitoring, and operation (Volmer et al., 2015). Under the perspective that those communities are complex adaptative systems, their modeling and characterization can be addressed from two different frameworks: (1) Supra-organismal approaches, taking the whole community as the modeling unit that interacts with the environment; and (2) population-based approaches, taking taxa as interacting units (Song et al., 2014). These types of characterizations could be used to improve the design and engineering of bioreactors, following rational strategies such as microbiome engineering, bioaugmentation or horizontal gene flow.

'Omics' research fields, such as functional metagenomics and sequence-driven screening have become a powerful tool to generate input information for the modeling. Through targeted sequencing of hypervariable regions of highly conserved genes, such as the 16S ribosomal RNA gene, it has been possible to develop population-based characterizations of microbial communities associated to pollution. This strategy has evidenced higher diversities in orders of magnitude than those assumed through culture-dependent approaches (Lovley, 2003). Meanwhile, through the functional metagenomics, the genomic repertoire of the whole community can be unraveled (Ufarté et al., 2015), allowing the development of supra-organismal characterizations of microbiomes that reveal the functional potential of them.

Attempts combining both approaches to characterize the dynamics in function and composition of microbial communities from bioreactors, have been successful for the understanding of their functional adaptation in the presence of pollutants and the identification of key metabolic processes to improve bioremediation. However, the alarming pollution rates that are currently going through, are demanding not only the improvement of bioremediation strategies already established, but also the elaboration of new strategies to disperse directly in the environment those microbial pathways that effectively remove pollutants, which could include molecular mechanisms such as mobile gene cassettes and massive horizontal gene transfer (de Lorenzo, 2017).

Following this perspective, the present project is presenting one of the most complete characterizations of microbial communities from bioreactors treating acid mine drainage (AMD) to identify key metabolic processes for its bioremediation. Combining targeted metagenomics and functional metagenomics, dynamics of the population over the treatment time and a complete supra-organismal characterization of these microbiomes were obtained. Though these approaches, functionalities overrepresented along the treatment time were identified, searching for good candidates that could be disseminated throughout AMD-impacted environments to accelerate their restoration. As dispersion mechanisms, a conjugative plasmid was tested to analyze the possibility of generating a massive horizontal gene transfer through AMD-impacted microbiomes (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Scheme representing research pathways that guided the formulation of this project.

The AMD is the major waste generated by the mining industry (Akcil and Koldas, 2006c). It is characterized by low pH and high concentration of metals and sulfate (Chen *et al.*, 2016). As this type of waste has a serious impact on human health and ecosystems, its control, containment and treatment are some of the main environmental challenges (Jennings *et al.*, 2008). One of the alternatives to cope with this issue is the use of Biochemical Passive Reactors (BPRs), which consist of columns filled with a reactive mixture composed of organic and inorganic substrates and their microbiological load, through which it is flowing the AMD that is being remediated by the microbial communities. These systems are an ideal experimental scenario for

studying the functional adaptation of microbial communities to AMD, because it allows to track population and functional shifts of the microbiome once the selective pressure of the AMD starts, identifying the snapshot of taxa and genes present in the moment that effective bioremediation is occurring.

This doctoral thesis project, entitled “*Understanding microbiome supra-metabolism responses under strong selective pressures as a resource for designing synthetic gene arrangements encoding key co-selected functions for environmental biotechnology applications*” has, as a main general objective, to improve the overall knowledge of microbiome composition and functions selected under Acid Mine Drainage contamination challenge, using as a model ecosystems bioremediation reactors. By in-depth metagenomic surveys and data analyses and by integrating systems and synthetic biology approaches, a design strategy to define key functions that are linked to improved bioremediation was developed, followed by the proposal of customized constructed genetic tools to spread and enhance such functions in the environmental microbiome. Accordingly, this doctoral thesis project was developed under the following specific objectives: i) to establish a state-of-the-art of the research topic of interest; ii) to characterize the supra-metabolism, identifying the activities that are simultaneously co-selected in microbial communities under strong selected pressures, such as AMD pollution; and iii) to propose the design of a synthetic construct to spread the key functions identified, in order to improve bioremediation processes.

This thesis presents the results for each of the specific objectives in chapters in format of independent scientific reports suitable for international peer-review (Chapters 1 to 3). Chapter 1 is presenting an original state-of-the-art conceptual framework of the research topics of interest, namely an integrative perspective of bioremediation, suprametabolism, microbial communities under AMD challenge, and bioreactors and microbiome composition. There is also included a detailed description of the advantages of using ‘omics’ in the field of bioremediation. Additionally, this chapter advances the definition and characterization, in this context, of supra-metabolism, reanalyzing in a composite comparative fashion the information available about microbiome composition in AMD ecosystems reported from different parts of the world, extracting and summarizing inclusive inferences and outlooks. 16S sequence data of 9 previously published studies were used to perform a population-based characterization, including predicted functional profiles from the microbial communities. Chapter 2 combines targeted metagenomics and functional metagenomics to characterize, in a very detailed fashion, the shifts and dynamics of the microbial diversity, functional potential variations, and gene abundances of BPRs’ microbiomes during the AMD treatment, identifying those functions of increased frequency during effective bioremediation. Chapter 3 describes the experiments performed to test the promiscuity of a conjugative plasmid designed with the precise purpose to be a tool to generate massive horizontal gene transfer inside AMD-impacted microbiomes, as a required essential resource for gene biougmentation for improved AMD bioremediation. In this chapter is also included the proposal of 3 synthetic modules to introduce specific genes inside the conjugative vector to spread key functions that could improve AMD bioremediation. Last section corresponds to a general discussion, conclusion, and remarks.

2.2 References

- Adams, G.O., Fufeyin, P.T., Okoro, S.E., and Ehinomen, I. (2015) Bioremediation, Biostimulation and Bioaugmentation: A Review. *Int J Environ Bioremediation Biodegrad* 3: 28–39.
- Akcil, A. and Koldas, S. (2006) Acid Mine Drainage (AMD): causes , treatment and case studies. 14: 1139–1145.
- Azubuike, C.C., Chikere, C.B., and Okpokwasili, G.C. (2016) Bioremediation techniques–classification based on site of application: principles, advantages, limitations and prospects. *World J Microbiol Biotechnol* 32: 1–18.
- Chen, L. xing, Huang, L. nan, Méndez-García, C., Kuang, J. liang, Hua, Z. shuang, Liu, J., and Shu, W. sheng (2016) Microbial communities, processes and functions in acid mine drainage ecosystems. *Curr Opin Biotechnol* 38: 150–158.
- Jagmann, N. and Philipp, B. (2014) Reprint of Design of synthetic microbial communities for biotechnological production processes. *J Biotechnol* 192: 293–301.
- Jennings, S.R., Blicher, S., Neuman, P., and Dennis, R. (2008) Acid mine drainage and effects on fish health and ecology: a review. *Reclam Res Gr* 1: 1–26.
- de Lorenzo, V. (2017) Seven microbial bio-processes to help the planet. *Microb Biotechnol* 0: 5–8.
- de Lorenzo, V., Marliere, P., and Sole, R. (2016) Bioremediation at a global scale: from the test tube to planet Earth. *Microb Biotechnol* 9: 618–625.
- Lovley, D.R. (2003) Cleaning up with genomics: applying molecular biology to bioremediation. *Nat Rev Microbiol* 1: 35–44.
- Song, H.-S., Cannon, W., Beliaev, A., and Konopka, A. (2014) Mathematical Modeling of Microbial Community Dynamics: A Methodological Review. *Processes* 2: 711–752.
- Ufarté, L., Laville, É., Duquesne, S., and Potocki-Veronese, G. (2015) Metagenomics for the discovery of pollutant degrading enzymes. *Biotechnol Adv* 33: 1845–1854.
- Villegas-plazas, M., Sanabria, J., and Junca, H. (2019) A composite taxonomical and functional framework of microbiomes under acid mine drainage bioremediation systems. *J Environ Manage* 251: 109581.
- Volmer, J., Schmid, A., and Bühler, B. (2015) Guiding bioprocess design by microbial ecology. *Curr Opin Microbiol* 25: 25–32.
- Widder, S., Allen, R.J., Pfeiffer, T., Curtis, T.P., Wiuf, C., Sloan, W.T., et al. (2016) Challenges in microbial ecology: Building predictive understanding of community function and dynamics. *ISME J* 10: 2557–2568.

CHAPTER I

A composite taxonomical and functional framework of microbiomes under Acid Mine Drainage bioremediation systems

Marcela Villegas-Plazas^{1,2*}, Janeth Sanabria², Howard Junca¹

¹RG Microbial Ecology: Metabolism, Genomics & Evolution, Div. Ecogenomics & Holobionts, Microbiomas Foundation, LT11A, 250008, Chia, Colombia

²Environmental Microbiology and Biotechnology Laboratory, Engineering School of Environmental & Natural Resources, Engineering Faculty, Universidad del Valle, Cali, Colombia

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

Mining-industry is one of the most important activities in the economic development of many countries and produces highly significant alterations on the environment, mainly due to the release of a strong acidic metal-rich wastewater called acid mine drainage (AMD). Consequently, the establishment of multiple wastewater treatment strategies in AMD research remains a fundamental challenge in AMD research. Bioremediation, as a constantly-evolving multidisciplinary endeavor had been complemented during the last decades by novel tools of increasingly higher resolution such as those based on omic approaches, which are providing detailed insights into the ecology, evolution and mechanisms of microbial communities acting in bioremediation processes. This review specifically addresses, reanalyzes and reexamines in a composite comparative manner, the available sequence information and associated metadata available in public databases about AMD impacted microbial communities; summarizing our understanding of its composition and functions, and proposing potential genetic enhancements for improved bioremediation strategies. 16S rRNA gene-targeted sequencing data from 9 studies previously published including AMD systems reported and studied around the world, were collected and reanalyzed to compare and identify the core and most abundant genera in four distinct AMD ecosystems: surface biofilm, water, impacted soils/sediments and bioreactor microbiomes. We determined that the microbial communities of bioreactors were the most diverse in bacterial types detected. The metabolic pathways predicted strongly suggest the key role of syntrophic communities with denitrification, methanogenesis, manganese, sulfate, and iron reduction. The perspectives to explore the dynamics of engineering systems by high-throughput sequencing and biochemical techniques are discussed and foreseen application of synthetic biology and omics exploration on improved AMD biotransformation are proposed.

Keywords: Microbial communities, AMD ecosystems, AMD bioremediation, bioreactors microbiome, predicted functional profiles.

Disclaimer: A different version of this chapter was published as a review article in:

Journal of Environmental Management (ISSN: 0301-4797), Volume 251, 1 December 2019, 109581

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.109581>.

1.1 Introduction

Coal mining-industry plays an important role in the economic development of many countries but produces highly significant alterations on the environment, by releasing acid mine drainage (AMD) (Kefeni et al., 2017), a strong acidic metal-rich wastewater formed when sulfide minerals from the rocks reacts with water and oxygen (Candeias et al., 2014) polluting and damaging the quality of essential ecosystem services like water for human consumption and soils for agriculture.

Currently, over 7269 million tonnes of hard coal are produced worldwide (World Coal Association - <https://www.worldcoal.org/coal/coal-mining>) and the generation of AMD occurs in all scenarios. To discard AMD untreated is unsustainable: it causes adverse effects on the quality of groundwater and surface waters, destroys ecosystems, corrodes infrastructure and negatively affects human health (Simate and Ndlovu, 2014). Consequently, treatment strategies have remained a fundamental challenge in AMD research. There are several physicochemical treatments methods such as electrochemical precipitation, filtration and sorption (Genty et al., 2018), and several bioremediation applications using sulfate-reducing bacteria (Papirio et al., 2012) which are currently used.

The simplest and cheapest method used to treat this type of waste is to increase the pH of the effluent to convert soluble metals into insoluble forms, however, this strategy is not selective and generates large quantities of solid sludge for disposal (Eccles, 1999). As other physicochemical treatments, this method implies high operational costs, low efficiency, and it produces secondary pollution (Hussain et al., 2016). This fact has driven research efforts to develop and improve bioremediation treatments as a plausible economic and sustainable alternative to achieve the restoration of AMD-impacted environments (Estrada Rendon et al., 1999; Carmen M. Neculita, Gérald J. Zagury, 2007; Neculita et al., 2008).

Bioremediation in the case of AMD aims the acceleration of pollutant transformation to compounds or physical chemical conditions of lower environmental impact. This could generally be achieved by improving the biochemical process required or by eliminating its limiting factors (Solé et al., 2015; de Lorenzo et al., 2016). Nowadays, the use of bacteria as tools to carry out the key reactions for restoration is considered one of the most promising and proven straightforward strategy. In contrast to organic contaminants, inorganic pollutants as those from the AMD cannot be mineralized, thus, under this context, bioremediation is achieved by altering the transport properties of pollutants (Kumar et al., 2018). Immobilization, transformation or mobilization of inorganic contaminants are possible through several processes mediated by bacteria, among the most important are biosorption, bioaccumulation, oxidation, and reduction (Mulligan and Galvez-Cloutier, 2003).

One of the main concerns in many studies about bioremediation is the final output, either by *in-situ* or *ex-situ* strategies (Techtmann and Hazen, 2016); however, since the microorganisms are the drivers for bioremediation, its effectiveness relies in understanding the mechanisms, functions and genes they have to be able to grow in highly contaminated places, and how pollution might induce such specific biological functionalities inside a microbial community (Kapley and Purohit, 2009). In order to better predict the fate of a contaminant, its effects in the microbial communities impacted, and how members of these communities could help to bioremediate it, a detailed and comprehensive understanding of the influences

in composition, structure, dynamics, metabolism, and functions of the environmental microbiome performing the process is a must.

Bioremediation is a constantly-evolving multidisciplinary endeavor, and as such, some of the processes are being reevaluated and further explored with the help of novel tools of increasingly higher resolution as those based on omic approaches. They provide key insights in the ecology, evolution, and mechanisms of microbial communities acting in bioremediation (Vilchez-Vargas *et al.*, 2010; Harms and Junca, 2014). This review specifically addresses, reanalyzes, and reexamines, in a composite comparative fashion, the information available about microbiome composition in the bioremediation of acid mine drainage systems reported from different parts of the world, and integrative inferences and outlooks are extracted and summarized.

1.2 Engineering of bioremediation process: an opportunity to improve understanding of community dynamics and functional stability

Last decade, researchers have focused on developing innovative methodologies to track and optimize bioprocesses to increase the efficiency of AMD remediation. The basis of the process is the use of microorganisms to generate alkalinity and immobilize metals through the production of highly insoluble sulfides (Simate and Ndlovu, 2014). Alkalinization process may be achieved through reductive biochemical processes such as denitrification, methanogenesis, and manganese, sulfate and iron reduction, being the last two those with major significance in AMD wastewaters (Figure 1) (Coetser *et al.*, 2006).

Figure 1. Overview of main biochemical processes occurring in AMD bioremediation systems.

Engineering has played a fundamental role in the improvement of this strategy through the development of controlled operational systems such as bioreactors, and several advantages have derived from this technology (Sanabria, 2014). Bioreactors in all their types, compared with *in situ* bioremediations strategies, allow increased mass transfer rates through the microbial community, increase the contact microorganism/pollutant/nutrient and enable the possibility to control and optimize multiple environmental parameters such as temperature, pH or even type of electron donor/acceptor proportionated to the microorganisms (Robles-González *et al.*, 2008).

In the case of AMD, most bioremediation options are mediated by passive bioreactors, a low-cost alternative because they do not require the continuous addition of energy or chemicals to promote the AMD transformation (Genty and Bussire, 2011; Robinson-Lora and Brennan, 2011). Passive bioreactors are

biological engineering systems containing a mixture of a variety of materials such as compost, manure, organic wastes and/or alkaline agents (Biermann et al., 2014), through which the AMD flows and the fermentation of these components creates the anaerobic conditions that support the biological reduction of sulfate and metal precipitation (Figure 1) (Robinson-Lora and Brennan, 2011).

Besides obtaining significantly shorter treatment times using bioreactors, these engineered systems also provide the opportunity to develop specialized knowledge about the responses of microbial communities under strong selective pressures such as pollution. The understanding of how microbial communities interact with a pollutant has been identified as one of the major challenges to improve bioremediation strategies. Along with the exploration of contaminated environments, comprehensive analyses of engineering ecosystems provide key information on how the exposure to AMD influences the dynamics of microbial communities, and how the adaptation of their metabolic flux occurs.

The revolutionary improvements in high-throughput DNA sequencing technologies and the development of several new 'omics' research fields, have enabled several insights into the taxonomical composition, genes and metabolic pathways involved in pollutant transformation (Ufarté et al., 2015). The integration of molecular biology, systems biology, microbial ecology, and genetic engineering together with this information on AMD impacted microbiomes aims to design robust approaches to improve bioremediation processes.

1.3 Integrated omics-perspective for effective bioremediation

Meta-omics approaches manage to identify genes, pathways or metabolic functions of microbial communities (Segata et al., 2013) through culture-independent tools, such as metagenomics, metatranscriptomics, metaproteomics, and metabolomics (Handelsman, 2004). Their implementation in bioremediation studies has advanced our understanding of the physiological response of microbial communities during biotransformation of pollutants (Bundy et al., 2009; Lacerda and Reardon, 2009).

Metagenomics and metatranscriptomics assess the genomic composition, biological fitness and transcriptional within and across microbial community members (Segata et al., 2013; Wang and Zhang, 2014). These complementary tools can be applied to detect specific targeted genes or in whole shotgun sequencing surveys (Segata et al., 2013), and through them it has been possible to profile the taxonomic diversity and the relevant genes present in microbial communities impacted with pollutants (Ufarté et al., 2015; Bouhajja et al., 2016; Duarte et al., 2017; Panigrahi et al., 2019). Meanwhile, metaproteomics and metabolomics analyze all proteins and metabolites that can be recovered from an environmental sample. These techniques are, therefore, a very informative complement when combined with metagenomics and metatranscriptomics.

Targeted metagenomics based on sequence-driven screening is one of the most used strategies for taxonomic profiling of microbial communities (Suenaga, 2012). Through the sequencing of hypervariable regions of the 16S ribosomal RNA gene, it is possible to determine the taxonomical composition of bacteria and archaea communities inhabiting a given environmental matrix (Logares et al., 2014). The same strategy can be reduced to a function-driven screening using specific functional genes, such as the *dsrB* gene. For

example, massive sequencing of this gene would be an efficient strategy to profile the sulfate-reducing bacterial community from AMD impacted environments (Wang *et al.*, 2016).

The 16S rRNA gene-based strategy is a powerful tool for assessing the phylogenetic distribution of bacteria and archaea, but it does not provide insights into the communities' metabolic potential. Software packages had been designed to complement this approach through the prediction of the functional capability of communities. Among the most used are PICRUSt and Tax4Fun (Langille *et al.*, 2013; Aßhauer *et al.*, 2015). These packages use different algorithms to link phylogeny with inferred protein encoding gene content by taxonomical genomic proxies of reference strains with genomes sequenced. Despite potential limitations in reference representation, they produce a good correspondence between their outputs and the results of metagenomic shotgun sequencing approaches (Aßhauer *et al.*, 2015; Iwai *et al.*, 2016).

Development of 'omics' tools have shown that bioremediation is a case of multiscale complexity and should not be addressed from reductionistic approaches (de Lorenzo, 2008). Their implementation have also led the evolution of microbial ecology, generating new mathematical models to characterize microbiomes (Song *et al.*, 2014) and introducing integrative concepts such as the Microbial Environmental Interactome (MEI) (Larsen *et al.*, 2012). The MEI, defined as the complete set of potential interactions between microorganisms and their biological, chemical and physical environments, represents conceptually the same thing that had been previously defined by de Lorenzo as the bioremediation space (de Lorenzo, 2008), in which there are three dimensions directly related to effectiveness of any bioremediation process: the catabolic landscape, the chemical landscape and the abiotic landscape. These three dimensions refer to the genes of the microbial population (biological), the nutrients and electron donors/acceptors (chemical) and the micro/macro geography of the site where the pollutant transformation is occurring (physical of MEI) (de Lorenzo, 2008). From this perspective, those microbial communities involved in bioremediation are considered as complex adaptative systems (Song *et al.*, 2014) and to improve the processes, they should be studied covering data of composition, dynamics, and connectivity from the three dimensions.

1.4 Developing a metagenomic view of AMD ecosystems

Those advents related to the omics tools have allowed for a minute finer description of microbial diversity and its functionality, leading to new opportunities for expanding our understanding on how microorganisms respond to the presence of AMD, and the possible reasons for their dynamic shifts during bioremediation (Figure 2). Scaling these analyses from natural ecosystems to engineering environmental matrices where bioremediation is occurring, would allow to comprehensively detail the changes in composition and function from native population to adapted and evolved acclimatized selected communities, information particularly useful and necessary to improve AMD bioremediation strategies.

Figure 2. Integration approaches and rationale for conventional and omics-based engineered and synthetic enhancements of bioremediation by environmental microbiomes. Developing more efficient bioremediation strategies requires in-depth understanding of the relationship between microbial communities' structure and the presence of pollutant and their metabolic functioning. Molecular biology techniques are used across all strategies. The scheme is showing three general approaches; upper part, conventional, cultured-based and using natural bacterial communities and isolates; mid-section, using assembled microbial consortia; lower part, omics approaches coupled to synthetic and systems biology models. Credits on icons used: photo3idea-studio and freepik.com (www.flaticon.com)

Currently, it is possible to find about 100 studies that have investigated through culture-independent methods, the patterns in the distribution of microorganisms in AMD ecosystems; most of them were performed using clone screening, RFLP/DGGE and Sanger sequencing (some examples (Yang et al., 2007, 2014; Xiao et al., 2009; Xie et al., 2009)). Supplementary Table 1 is showing selected recent studies that had investigated microbial communities associated with AMD, restricted to those using high-throughput sequencing technologies and omics approaches. These studies have been carried out mostly on AMD-impacted soil and sediments, AMD water and AMD-water biofilms, and only a few have been focused on the microbial communities of bioreactors.

Here we summarize a comparative upgraded perspective of the microbial ecology of AMD by providing a comprehensive analysis of prokaryotic communities associated with different AMD ecosystems. Analyses were performed using sequence data from 9 previously published studies recovered from GenBank accession numbers and Sequence Read Archive (SRA) registered in Supplementary Table 2 (Auld et al., 2013; Brantner and Senko, 2014; Keshri et al., 2015; M. Sun et al., 2015; W. Sun et al., 2015; Gupta et al., 2017; Hao et al., 2017; Havig et al., 2017; Vasquez et al., 2018) The sequences represent 44 samples including AMD water,

AMD water biofilms, impacted soils and sediments and bioreactors. A Detailed description of bioinformatic methodology can be found in supplementary material.

Richness and alpha diversity of AMD associated microbial communities varied widely across the type of ecosystem; their complexity, assessed in terms of number of OTUs ranged from 100 to >4000. Communities inhabiting the AMD water and their surface biofilms were less diverse than those from impacted soils and sediments or bioreactors from AMD treatment (Figure 3), suggesting that despite the extreme conditions that represent the acidity and high concentrations of toxic metal and sulfate, community-level functional acclimatization occurs in response to the AMD perturbation. Therefore, impacted environments and even matrices from bioreactors are better sources for quantitative or metagenomic-based analyses of microbial ecology and community function than the AMD water itself.

Figure 3. Species richness and alpha-diversity of AMD microbiome compiled data and sampled ecosystem types.

At phylum-level, Proteobacteria, Acidobacteria, Firmicutes, Actinobacteria, and Nitrospirae have been reported as dominant lineages detected in AMD environments (Chen *et al.*, 2016; Teng *et al.*, 2017; Thavamani *et al.*, 2017). Our data compilation reaffirmed this and showed Proteobacteria (especially classes Alpha- and Gammaproteobacteria) as the most dominant phylum in both, AMD water and impacted environments. On the other hand, Cyanobacteria appeared as the predominant phylum in AMD surface biofilms, confirming that its presence is highly influenced by light exposure and drastically reduced beneath the surface (Mesa *et*

al., 2017). Other phyla such as Bacteroidetes, Chloroflexi, Spirochaete and Verrucomicrobia that appear as rare biosphere of AMD water and biofilms, reach high relative abundances (>5%) in samples from impacted soils, sediments and bioreactors (Figure 4), exhibiting the ubiquity of microorganisms that can evolve mechanisms to resist toxic pollutant stress and thrive noxious environments.

Figure 4. Joint accumulated microbiome composition of reviewed ecosystems under AMD selection. Relative frequencies of phyla with accumulation greater than 1% of the total compiled data for each ecosystem type. 1 AMD Biofilm; 2 AMD Water; 3 AMD-impacted environments; 4 Bioreactor.

1.4.1 AMD biofilm, water, and impacted environments

Inside the diversity of microbial communities inhabiting AMD water, acidophilic bacteria sulfur and/or iron-oxidizers are the predominant groups. The acidic nature and high concentration of dissolved metals exert strong selective pressure on microorganisms, favoring genera that have developed multiple stress resistance mechanisms to deal with the extreme environmental conditions. *Leptospirillum* (Chen et al., 2014), *Ferroplasma* (Kuang et al., 2013; Huang et al., 2016), *Ferrovum* (Hua et al., 2015; Hao et al., 2017), *Gallionella* (He et al., 2007), *Acidiphilium* (Auld et al., 2013), *Acidithrix* (Chen et al., 2016), *Sideroxydans* (Chen et al., 2014; Mühling et al., 2016), *Acidithiobacillus* (He et al., 2007; Auld et al., 2013) and *Nitrospira* (Chen et al., 2016) have been previously reported as the most common genera inhabiting AMD systems; in our compilation data, these genera represent, together with an unidentified *Cyanobacteria* a cumulative relative abundance greater than 63% in AMD biofilm samples, 31% in AMD water samples, 6% in AMD-impacted soils and sediments and less than 2% in bioreactor samples.

Considering that the isolation of these genera is difficult, hypotheses of their metabolisms are inferred from the metabolic reconstruction of metagenomic sequence data, which have shown the coexistence of obligated autotrophic and heterotrophic bacteria and archaea. *Ferrovum* has been recognized as the main carbon fixer

inside AMD microbial communities, fixing carbon via Calvin-Benson-Bassham cycle and, producing energy through ferrous iron oxidation (Hua et al., 2015). Metabolic reconstructions suggest that also *Leptospirillum* may perform carbon fixation but via the novel reductive tricarboxylic acid cycle (Hippe, 2000) and has found as the major nitrogen fixer in AMD water systems (Hua et al., 2015).

Through various attempts to culture and isolate microorganism from AMD water, a co-occurrence between *Ferrovum* and *Acidiphilium* has been inferred (Hedrich et al., 2009; Kuang et al., 2013; Hua et al., 2015); it has not been possible to obtain pure cultures but both mixed. Also in our data compilation, these two genera showed a positive correlation in AMD water and biofilm samples, which was reflected with a Spearman's rank coefficient > 0.9 (p-value < 0.01) (Barberan et al., 2012). Zheng-Shuang and collaborators argue that the presence of *Acidiphilium* facilitates the dominance of *Ferrovum* by degrading organic substances that are otherwise toxic to this genus (Hua et al., 2015).

The ecological roles and functional partitioning of the other dominant genera such as *Acidithrix* and *Sideroxydans* have been defined by the ability to perform dissimilatory oxide-reduction of iron (Jones and Barrie Johnson, 2015; Mühling et al., 2016), while *Nitrospira* has been distinguished by its growing via oxidation of nitrite to nitrate (Daims and Science, 2014). As for the generation of SO_4^{2-} and S^0 , it has been attributed to the activity of sulfur-oxidizing enzymes and the Sox system found in *Acidithiobacillus* (Hua et al., 2015) and to the activity of the metabolically versatile *Cyanobacteria*, which under sulfide-rich conditions can use sulfur as electron donor through anoxygenic photosynthesis (Havig et al., 2017).

Within the Archaea domain, *Ferroplasma* has been one of the most predominant genera found in AMD water samples (Xie et al., 2009). Yang and collaborators reported that all genera from the *Thermoplasmatales* order, which contains the most acidophilic microorganisms already known (Ferrer et al., 2007), are heterotrophic, except for *Ferroplasma* (Yang et al., 2014), which is a strictly chemolithoautotrophic which play an important role in the global iron-sulfur cycle (Potrykus et al., 2011). Contribution of this archaeon in the AMD generation is the catalysis of the weathering of sulfide minerals by regeneration of Fe^{+3} , which oxidize minerals (Potrykus et al., 2011).

Species richness and diversity of AMD impacted environments, such as soils, sediments and engineering ecosystems as the bioreactor matrices, are higher than those exhibited by the communities inhabiting the AMD water itself (Figure 3). This may be related to the least extreme pH and the significantly higher organic carbon contents. Previous reports have found that high and heterogeneous resource of carbon compounds influence high microbial diversity in soils (Zhou et al., 2002). This fact demonstrates that autochthonous microorganisms could acquire AMD tolerance using multiple metabolic processes, such as the high abundance of metal transporter genes, high expression of functions from iron and sulfur cycle or multiple diverse modes of carbon and nitrogen metabolism (Aguinaga et al., 2018). Such knowledge may guide the biochemical and genetic improvement of AMD bioremediation strategies.

While in AMD water and biofilms predominate sulfur and iron-oxidizers groups, the microbiome of not impacted soils is composed by a more balanced distribution of taxa related to all biogeochemical processes and regulating soil characteristics, as it is the availability of nitrogen, phosphorus and organic carbon pools (Fierer, 2017). The introduction of AMD into soils not previously impacted leads to rapid changes in soil microbiome and stimulates the predominance of phylotypes with the ability to perform oxidative

precipitation of Fe (Brantner and Senko, 2014). As the set of data analyzed here revealed (Figure 5), *Ferrovum*, *Shewanella*, *Geobacter*, *Metallibacterium* and *Gallionella* were some of the most abundant genera in samples from AMD-impacted soils and sediments and were previously associated with the iron metabolism; *Ferrovum*, *Metallibacterium* and *Gallionella* recognized as common iron-oxidizing bacteria (Brantner and Senko, 2014; M. Sun et al., 2015; Bartsch et al., 2017) and *Shewanella* and *Geobacter*, identified as some of the most important iron-reducing bacteria in AMD-polluted soils (M. Sun et al., 2015).

Along with the genera implicated in iron metabolism, within the most abundant genera inhabiting AMD-contaminated environments, bacteria related to sulfur and nitrogen metabolisms have been reported (Figure 5). Previous studies have found a dynamic and complex nitrogen cycle occurring with the presence of AMD, in which microbial communities likely obtained nitrogen resources via nitrogen fixation and ammonium assimilation (Havig et al., 2017). *Rhizobium*, *Acidithiobacillus*, *Leptospirillum* and *Gallionellaceae* were identified through metabolic metagenomics reconstructions as some of the most common nitrogen fixers in AMD-impacted environments (Chen et al., 2014; D'hondt et al., 2015; Liljeqvist et al., 2015). Besides, the frequency with which it has been also reported *Nitrospira* taxa suggests that the communities of AMD-contaminated environments contain active nitrate reducers as well (Havig et al., 2017).

Even though it has been also identified that this pollutant may limit denitrification due to the low pH and the interference of ferric iron acting as a competitive electron acceptor (Baeseman et al., 2006), *Halomonas*, it has been one of the most abundant genera found in AMD-polluted sites (Auld et al., 2013; M. Sun et al., 2015; W. Sun et al., 2015; Sun et al., 2016); its ecological role is uncertain (Auld et al., 2013) but is believed that includes some denitrifying and iron-oxidizing species (M. Sun et al., 2015). González-Domenech C. and colleges during a comprehensive study of denitrifying species of this genus found that *Halomonas* express the full suite of reductase enzymes necessary to oxidize nitrogen compounds to gaseous products (González-Domenech et al., 2010); these findings suggest that due to the extreme conditions that represent AMD contamination, *Halomonas* and other denitrifiers inhabiting polluted sites have adapted to obtain the maximum energy available from complete nitrate respiration, despite low pH and high concentrations of ferric iron.

Another rapid change in soil microbiome after the introduction of AMD, occurring possibly as a self-mitigation process, is the increase of metabolic activities that can generate alkalinity, such as anaerobic reductive processes resulting in iron or sulfate-reduction (Sánchez-andrea et al., 2014). This is evidenced within the structure of the microbial communities by the increased relative abundance of sulfate-reducers groups as *Desulfobacca*, *Desulfobacterium* and *Desulfatiglans* (M. Sun et al., 2015) and the previously mentioned iron-reducing bacteria *Shewanella* and *Geobacter*.

Figure 5. Heatmap representing the relative abundance of predominant genera in all microbiomes in ecosystems under AMD selection with data publicly available. As predominant genera all those with a relative abundance greater than 1% were considered. Each genus was associated with a type of metabolism, according to previous reports showing experimentally such physiological features, some have been studied also through genomic approaches and others with biochemical data from cultures. Un prefix refers to unidentified genera.

1.4.2 AMD bioremediation engineering systems

In the same way that occurs in natural attenuation, AMD bioremediation strategies seek to increase alkalization through biochemical processes such as microbial anaerobic reductions (Figure 1). There are some studies that have focused on the application of molecular methods, including real-time PCR, TRFLP or DGGE to understand metabolic capabilities of the microorganisms present in bioreactors (Hallberg *et al.*;

Krinks, 2007; Pruden et al., 2007; Pereyra et al., 2008), but there are still few studies using meta-omics approaches for investigating their community functional potential and activity, which would contribute to opening the “black box” of AMD bioremediation (Vanwonterghem et al., 2014; Aoyagi et al., 2017; Vasquez et al., 2018). Both of these works were based on biochemical passive reactors which have a reactive mixture with high organic load and soil or sediments as inoculum (Aoyagi et al., 2017; Vasquez et al., 2018), which means that their microbial communities represent natural environmental microbiomes adapted to the continuous presence of AMD.

Alpha diversity index of compiled data (Figure 3) showed that bioreactor communities were much more diverse than those from AMD water and impacted environments, suggesting that bioengineering systems could be an appropriate model to investigate the link between microbial community dynamics and the process and functional stability.

Additional diversity detected on bioreactor samples was represented mostly by genera from the phyla *Bacteroidetes*, *Firmicutes* and *Proteobacteria*, which have been reported as the predominant phyla in different types of sulfate-reducing bioreactors during stable operation of AMD treatment (Hallberg et al.; Zhao et al., 2010; Aoyagi et al., 2017; Vasquez et al., 2018). Comparing to AMD water and impacted environments, in bioreactors, there is an enrichment of strictly anaerobic populations. Most genera within the phylum *Firmicutes* were from the order *Clostridiales*, recognized due to its ability to hydrolyze cellulosic biomass (Schwarz, 2001) and/or by being fermentative microorganisms producers of organic acids (Aoyagi et al., 2017). Likewise, the phylum *Bacteroidetes* contains highly efficient degraders of complex carbohydrates that produce some simple sugars, organic acids, and alcohols, compounds that are essentially used by sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB) as carbon substrate (Vasquez et al., 2018). Furthermore, inside *Proteobacteria* phylum (and especially in *Deltaproteobacteria* class) are contained most of the SRB reported in AMD treatments. Analysis of compiled data showed as significantly enriched genera in this engineering scenario (1-way ANOVA p-values <0.01) to *Desulfatirhabdium*, *Desulfovibrio*, *Desulfomicrobium*, *Desulfobulbus*, *Desulfobacula* and three more unidentified genera from the families *Desulfobacteraceae* and *Desulfobulbaceae*.

Regarding the most abundant genera, considering here those with a relative abundance greater than 1% (Figure 5), the predominance of phyla *Proteobacteria*, *Bacteroidetes* and *Firmicutes* were maintained with the addition of some representatives from the phylum *Spirochaetes*. In contrast to what occurred in environmental samples (AMD water, biofilm, and impacted soils and sediments), in bioreactors, there was no dominance of phylotypes involved in iron metabolism and sulfur-oxidation but rather appeared with a more relative accumulation, sulfate-reducing genera, sugar-fermenting bacteria and complexes organic compounds degraders. Aoyagi and collaborators have previously reported that the accumulation and co-existences of these 3 phyla may be an important indicator of stable operation of AMD treatment (Aoyagi et al., 2017).

Additional features that stand out from the bioreactor community are the emergence of methanogenic archaeon such as *Methanobrevibacter*, *Methanobacteriaceae*, and *Methanomassiliococcaceae*. On the one hand, the low abundance in which they are detected could indicate a possible inhibition of methanogenesis by competition with microorganisms such as nitrate, sulfate, and iron reducers (Roden and Wetzell, 2003; Van Bodegom et al., 2004). On the other hand, stands out also the detection of taxa reported as strictly aerobic

microorganisms, such as *Arthrobacter*, *Fluviicola*, *Flavobacterium*, *Pedobacter* or *Lysinibacillus*, these might be playing a role in detoxification of exogenous or metabolic oxygen.

Finally, another peculiarity about the microbial communities of bioreactors is that despite being controlled engineering systems, the taxonomic identification or the metabolism of many of their representative phylotypes are still unknown. The portion of unidentified OTUs and the number of genera from which there are still no references of possible ecological roles is much greater in these systems than in AMD water, biofilms, and impacted environments. This may be related not only to the difficulty to culture them but also to the fact that the great diversity of these systems requires higher sequencing depth to recover their complete genomes or to achieve closer cultured isolates. Bioreactors and other engineering environments are thus manageable systems to integrate, through meta-omics approaches, the theories and concepts of microbial community dynamics and the stability of function and process, and a source to retrieve and maintain bacterial groups not yet fully described.

1.5 Predicted functional profiles of AMD communities

Metabolic potential of AMD communities has been identified using metatranscriptomics and whole metagenome sequencing (WMS) in previous studies (Hu et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2014; Hua et al., 2015).

Figure 6. Bar plot summarizing functional profiles predicted using the R package Tax4Fun. KO abundance of 155 pathways grouped in 18 functional and metabolic categories and the pathway map showing the main categories.

Genes involved in energy production, carbon metabolism, nitrogen metabolism, oxidative phosphorylation, amino acid metabolism, and biogenesis have been reported as the dominant ones in AMD systems (Chen et al., 2014; Hua et al., 2015). This matches the predictive profiles presented in figure 6, which were created using Tax4Fun on the compiled data (Supplementary Table 3). As it was mentioned above, Tax4Fun is a powerful

tool to predict functional profiles of prokaryotic communities from 16S rRNA gene sequences using functional information derived from genomes available in public databases (Aßhauer et al., 2015).

Predicted profiles of AMD water, biofilms, impacted environments and bioreactor samples comprised 155 pathways summarized in 18 functional and metabolic categories (Figure 6). The uniformity in the potential of central pathways, both in predicted profiles and in those derived from WMS (Chen et al., 2014; Hua et al., 2015) indicates that regardless of extreme conditions, microbial communities are functionally adapted to maintain the basic cellular machinery. It is interesting that, as it has been reported by Zheng-Shuang and collaborators, pathways like two-component regulatory systems and ATP-binding cassette transporters (ABC transporters) were also highly represented in predictions (Figure 6), indicating the active response of microbial communities to the AMD presence and the changing environment (Pascale et al., 2002). In the case of bioreactor samples, the unexpected prediction of oxidative phosphorylation, highlight the importance of the possible detoxification role played by strict aerobics in this anaerobic environment.

Analyzing the metabolism of predominant taxa in the AMD systems, sulfur metabolism is preponderant. However, these predicted profiles showed that, while the sulfur metabolism is indeed detected, it is representing a relatively low fraction of the total metabolism, being less than 1%. This is consistent with the results of metagenomics works where sequences from genes involved in sulfur metabolism did not dominate the transcript pools of analyzed AMD communities (Chen et al., 2014). This proportion was maintained in both AMD natural environments and bioreactors, but with a difference in the dominant reaction; figure 7 is representing the KO abundance of 5 pathways from the sulfur metabolism and showed that sulfide-oxidation is greater in AMD biofilms and water, while sulfate-reduction is greater in bioreactors. These findings evidence that although the transformation of acid drainage relays mainly on sulfur-oxidizing and sulfate-reducing bacteria, it is necessary to analyze the whole ecosystem with all the accompanying diversity to understand the supra-metabolism and thus improve bioremediation strategies.

1.6 Conclusions and remarks

The revolutionary improvements in high-throughput DNA sequencing technologies and the development of several new 'omics' research fields have become fundamental tools to allow the interaction between microbial ecologists and engineers, considering that through them it is possible to characterize community structure and supra-metabolism (Amit et al., 2016). Regarding AMD systems, we are only now beginning to link community dynamics with the stability of process and functions in engineered systems for bioremediation, and the detailed development of this knowledge will be fundamental to improve AMD bioremediation strategies.

This review, accomplished to reanalyze and reexamine in a composite comparative direction, the information available about microbial communities associated with AMD. Data compiled here came from different AMD systems, including AMD surface biofilm, water, impacted soils and sediments and bioreactors for the AMD treatment.

Figure 7. Bubble plot representing the KO abundance of 5 sub metabolic pathways that are part of the sulfur metabolism.

The main findings revealed that communities inhabiting the AMD water and their biofilms are less diverse than those from impacted soils and sediments or bioreactors; which suggests that despite the extreme conditions that represent the acidity and high concentrations of toxic metal and sulfate, community-level functional acclimatization occurs in response to the AMD perturbation. Sulfur and iron-oxidizers genera, such as *Leptospirillum*, *Ferroplasma*, *Ferrovum*, *Gallionella*, and *Acidithrix* were predominant in AMD water and biofilms, while in AMD-impacted soils and sediments stood out iron-reducing bacteria such as *Shewanella* and *Geobacter*. In comparison with AMD water and impacted environments, in bioreactor samples, there was an enrichment of strictly anaerobic populations, and principally sulfate-reducing bacteria from *Deltaproteobacteria* class, such as *Desulfatirhabdium*, *Desulfovibrio*, *Desulfomicrobium*, *Desulfobulbus*, and *Desulfobacula*.

The application of bioinformatics tools such as Tax4Fun to the compiled data analyzed here resulted in a more holistic understanding of the link between bacteria and AMD. Genes involved in energy production, carbon metabolism, amino acid metabolism, and biogenesis were predicted as dominant in all the systems. Sulfur metabolism, which participates in the generations and bioremediation of AMD had a place lower than 1% in the predicted profiles, which it seems low for a leading metabolic role in AMD systems but is comparatively higher than in many ecosystems (Ding et al., 2015; Mendes et al., 2015). Another fascinating fact revealed by these predictions was that, while there is a robustness of metabolic processes between the AMD systems, the difference between aqueous and colloidal phases implies some localized metabolic processes, as occurring with SOX systems and the sulfate reduction.

Finally, a remarkable fact from this composite comparative approach is that, among all the analyzed ecosystems, bioreactor samples presented the highest proportion of non-identified OTUs and the highest number of genera from which there are still no references of possible ecological roles. This discovery reveals that these engineering systems are the largest source of metabolic diversity from AMD ecosystems and

therefore, they represent a great potential to improve the understanding of AMD biotransformation steps. It would be important to move toward high-throughput sequencing assays, including detailed structure–function analyses. Bioreactors and other engineering environments emerge as thus manageable systems to integrate, through meta-omics approaches, the theories, and concepts of microbial community dynamics and the stability of function and process. These studies will help us to move toward a more comprehensive metagenomic view of microbial metabolism inside AMD and the improvement of its bioremediation strategies.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the financial support from Departamento Administrativo de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación – COLCIENCIAS – through doctoral fellowship “Beca de Estudios Doctorales Nacionales 727” granted to M. Villegas-Plazas and the access to computing infrastructure kindly provided by Prof Ericsson Coy Ph.D. INQUIBIO-UMNG.

1.7 References

- Aguinaga, O.E., McMahon, A., White, K.N., Dean, A.P., Pittman, J.K., and Dean, A.P. (2018) Microbial Community Shifts in Response to Acid Mine Drainage Pollution Within a Natural Wetland Ecosystem. *Front Microbiol* 9: 1–14.
- Aoyagi, T., Hamai, T., Hori, T., Sato, Yuki, Kobayashi, M., Sato, Yuya, et al. (2017) Hydraulic retention time and pH affect the performance and microbial communities of passive bioreactors for treatment of acid mine drainage. *AMB Express* 7: 1–11.
- Alshauer, K.P., Wemheuer, B., Daniel, R., and Meinicke, P. (2015) Tax4Fun: Predicting functional profiles from metagenomic 16S rRNA data. *Bioinformatics* 31: 2882–2884.
- Auld, R.R., Myre, M., Mykytczuk, N.C.S., Leduc, L.G., and Merritt, T.J.S. (2013) Characterization of the microbial acid mine drainage microbial community using culturing and direct sequencing techniques. *J Microbiol Methods* 93: 108–115.
- Baeseman, J.L., Smith, R.L., and Silverstein, J. (2006) Denitrification potential in stream sediments impacted by acid mine drainage: Effects of pH, various electron donors, and iron. *Microb Ecol* 51: 232–241.
- Barberan, A., Bates, S.T., Casamayor, E.O., and Fierer, N. (2012) Using network analysis to explore co-occurrence patterns in soil microbial communities. *Isme J* 6: 343–351.
- Bartsch, S., Gensch, A., Stephan, S., Doetsch, A., and Gescher, J. (2017) *Metallibacterium scheffleri*: genomic data reveal a versatile metabolism. *FEMS Microbiol Ecol* 93: 1–10.
- Biermann, V., Lillicrap, A.M., Magana, C., Price, B., Bell, R.W., and Oldham, C.E. (2014) Applicability of passive compost bioreactors for treatment of extremely acidic and saline waters in semi-arid climates. *Water Res* 55: 83–94.
- Van Bodegom, P.M., Scholten, J.C.M., and Stams, A.J.M. (2004) Direct inhibition of methanogenesis by ferric iron. *FEMS Microbiol Ecol* 49: 261–268.
- Bouhajja, E., Agathos, S.N., and George, I.F. (2016) Metagenomics: Probing pollutant fate in natural and engineered ecosystems. *Biotechnol Adv* 34: 1413–1426.
- Brantner, J.S. and Senko, J.M. (2014) Response of soil-associated microbial communities to intrusion of coal mine-derived acid mine drainage. *Environ Sci Technol* 48: 8556–8563.
- Bundy, J.G., Davey, M.P., and Viant, M.R. (2009) Environmental metabolomics: A critical review and future perspectives. *Metabolomics* 5: 3–21.
- Candeias, C., Ávila, P.F., Silva, E.F. Da, Ferreira, A., Salgueiro, A.R., and Teixeira, J.P. (2014) Acid mine drainage from the Panasqueira mine and its influence on Zêzere river (Central Portugal). *J African Earth Sci* 99: 705–712.
- Carmen M. Neculita, Gérald J. Zagury, and V.K. (2007) Short-Term And Long-Term Bioreactors For Acid Mine Drainage Treatment PART I : Acid Mine Drainage. *Proc Annu Int Conf Soils, Sediments, Water Energy* 12: 2–9.

- Chen, L.-X., Hu, M., Huang, L.-N., Hua, Z.-S., Kuang, J.-L., Li, S.-J., and Shu, W.-S. (2014) Comparative metagenomic and metatranscriptomic analyses of microbial communities in acid mine drainage. *ISME J* 9: 1579–1592.
- Chen, L. xing, Huang, L. nan, Méndez-García, C., Kuang, J. liang, Hua, Z. shuang, Liu, J., and Shu, W. sheng (2016) Microbial communities, processes and functions in acid mine drainage ecosystems. *Curr Opin Biotechnol* 38: 150–158.
- Coetser, S.E., Pulles, W., Heath, R.G.M., and Cloete, T.E. (2006) Chemical Characterisation of Organic Electron Donors For Sulfate Reduction For Potential Use in Acid Mine Drainage Treatment. *Biodegradation* 17: 67–77.
- D'hondt, S., Inagaki, F., Zarikian, C.A., Abrams, L.J., Dubois, N., Engelhardt, T., et al. (2015) Presence of oxygen and aerobic communities from sea floor to basement in deep-sea sediments. *Nat Geosci* 8: 299–304.
- Daims, H. and Science, E. (2014) Tha Family Nitrospiraceae. 733–749.
- Ding, J., Zhang, Y., Deng, Y., Cong, J., Lu, H., Sun, X., et al. (2015) Integrated metagenomics and network analysis of soil microbial community of the forest timberline. *Sci Rep* 5: 1–10.
- Duarte, M., Nielsen, A., Camarinha-Silva, A., Vilchez-Vargas, R., Bruls, T., Wos-Oxley, M.L., et al. (2017) Functional soil metagenomics: Elucidation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon degradation potential following 12 years of *in situ* bioremediation. *Environ Microbiol*.
- Eccles, H. (1999) Treatment of metal-contaminated wastes: Why select a biological process? *Trends Biotechnol* 17: 462–465.
- Estrada Rendon, C.M., Amara, G., Leonard, P., Tobin, J., Roussy, J., and Degorce-Dumas, J.R. (1999) Acid Mine Drainage (AMD) treatment by sulphate reducing bacteria. *Process Metall* 9: 577–585.
- Ferrer, M., Golyshina, O. V., Beloqui, A., Golyshin, P.N., and Timmis, K.N. (2007) The cellular machinery of *Ferroplasma acidiphilum* is iron-protein-dominated. *Nature* 445: 91–94.
- Fierer, N. (2017) Embracing the unknown: Disentangling the complexities of the soil microbiome. *Nat Rev Microbiol* 15: 579–590.
- Genty, T. and Bussière, B. (2011) Passive treatment of acid mine drainage: Repeatability for sulphate reducing passive bioreactor column efficiency testing. *11th Int Mine ...* 313–318.
- Genty, T., Bussière, B., Benzaazoua, M., Neculita, C.M., and Zagury, G.J. (2018) Iron removal in highly contaminated acid mine drainage using passive biochemical reactors. 1833–1843.
- González-Domenech, C.M., Martínez-Checa, F., Béjar, V., and Quesada, E. (2010) Denitrification as an important taxonomic marker within the genus *Halomonas*. *Syst Appl Microbiol* 33: 85–93.
- Gupta, A., Dutta, A., Sarkar, J., Paul, D., Panigrahi, M.K., and Sar, P. (2017) Metagenomic exploration of microbial community in mine tailings of Malanjkhand copper project, India. *Genomics Data*.
- Hallberg, K.B., Rolfe, S., and Johnson, D.B. The microbiology of passive remediation technologies for mine drainage treatment.
- Handelsman, J. (2004) Metagenomics: Application of Genomics to Uncultured Microorganisms. *Microbiol Mol Biol Rev* 68: 669–685.
- Hao, C., Wei, P., Pei, L., Du, Z., Zhang, Y., and Lu, Y. (2017) Significant seasonal variations of microbial community in an acid mine drainage lake in Anhui Province, China. *Environ Pollut* 1–10.
- Harms, H. and Junca, H. (2014) Editorial overview: Environmental Biotechnology. *Curr Opin Biotechnol* 27: 5–6.
- Havig, J.R., Grettenberger, C., and Hamilton, T.L. (2017) Geochemistry and microbial community composition across a range of acid mine drainage impact and implications for the Neoproterozoic-Paleoproterozoic transition. *J Geophys Res Biogeosciences* 122: 1404–1422.
- He, Z., Xiao, S., Xie, X., Zhong, H., Hu, Y., Li, Q., et al. (2007) Molecular diversity of microbial community in acid mine drainages of Yunfu sulfide mine. *Extremophiles* 11: 305–314.
- Hedrich, S., Heinzl, E., Seifert, J., and Schlomann, M. (2009) Isolation of novel iron-oxidizing bacteria from an acid mine water treatment plant. *Adv Mater Res* 71–73: 125–128.
- Hippe, H. (2000) *Leptospirillum* gen. nov. (ex Markosyan 1972), nom. rev., including *Leptospirillum ferrooxidans* sp. nov. (ex Markosyan 1972), nom. rev. and *Leptospirillum thermoferrooxidans* sp. nov. (Golovacheva et al. 1992). *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 50: 501–503.
- Hu, Q., Liang, Y.L., Yin, H.Q., Guo, X., Hao, X.D., Liu, X.D., and Qiu, G.Z. (2013) Metagenomic Insights into the Microbial Community Diversity between Leaching Heap and Acid Mine Drainage. *Adv Mater Res* 825: 141–144.

- Hua, Z.-S., Han, Y.-J., Chen, L.-X., Liu, J., Hu, M., Li, S.-J., et al. (2015) Ecological roles of dominant and rare prokaryotes in acid mine drainage revealed by metagenomics and metatranscriptomics. *ISME J* 9: 1280–94.
- Huang, L.N., Kuang, J.L., and Shu, W.S. (2016) Microbial Ecology and Evolution in the Acid Mine Drainage Model System. *Trends Microbiol* 24: 581–593.
- Hussain, A., Hasan, A., Javid, A., and Qazi, J.I. (2016) Exploited application of sulfate-reducing bacteria for concomitant treatment of metallic and non-metallic wastes: a mini review. *3 Biotech* 6:
- Iwai, S., Weinmaier, T., Schmidt, B.L., Albertson, D.G., Poloso, N.J., Dabbagh, K., and DeSantis, T.Z. (2016) Piphillin: Improved prediction of metagenomic content by direct inference from human microbiomes. *PLoS One* 11: 1–18.
- Jones, R.M. and Barrie Johnson, D. (2015) *Acidithrix ferrooxidans* gen. nov., sp. nov.; a filamentous and obligately heterotrophic, acidophilic member of the Actinobacteria that catalyzes dissimilatory oxido-reduction of iron. *Res Microbiol* 166: 111–120.
- Kapley, A. and Purohit, H.J. (2009) Genomic tools in bioremediation. 108–113.
- Kefeni, K.K., Msagati, T.A.M., and Mamba, B.B. (2017) Acid mine drainage: Prevention, treatment options, and resource recovery: A review. *J Clean Prod.*
- Keshri, J., Mankazana, B.B.J., and Momba, M.N.B. (2015) Profile of bacterial communities in South African mine-water samples using Illumina next-generation sequencing platform. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 99: 3233–3242.
- Krinks, J. (2007) Microbial Assessment of a Bioremediation System Treating Acid Mine Drainage. *Russ Coll Eng Technol Ohio Univ.*
- Kuang, J.L., Huang, L.N., Chen, L.X., Hua, Z.S., Li, S.J., Hu, M., et al. (2013) Contemporary environmental variation determines microbial diversity patterns in acid mine drainage. *ISME J* 7: 1038–1050.
- Kumar, V., Shahi, S., and Singh, S. (2018) Bioremediation: An Eco-Sustainable Approach for Restoration of Contaminated sites. In, *Microbial Bioprospecting for Sustainable Development.*, p. 396.
- Lacerda, C.M.R. and Reardon, K.F. (2009) Environmental proteomics: Applications of proteome profiling in environmental microbiology and biotechnology. *Briefings Funct Genomics Proteomics* 8: 75–87.
- Langille, M.G.I., Zaneveld, J., Caporaso, J.G., McDonald, D., Knights, D., Reyes, J.A., et al. (2013) Predictive functional profiling of microbial communities using 16S rRNA marker gene sequences. *Nat Biotechnol* 31: 814–821.
- Larsen, P., Hamada, Y., and Gilbert, J. (2012) Modeling microbial communities: Current, developing, and future technologies for predicting microbial community interaction. *J Biotechnol* 160: 17–24.
- Liljeqvist, M., Ossandon, F.J., Gonz, C., Rajan, S., Stell, A., Valdes, J., et al. (2015) Metagenomic analysis reveals adaptations to a cold-adapted lifestyle in a low-temperature. 1–12.
- Logares, R., Sunagawa, S., Salazar, G., Cornejo-Castillo, F.M., Ferrera, I., Sarmiento, H., et al. (2014) Metagenomic 16S rDNA Illumina tags are a powerful alternative to amplicon sequencing to explore diversity and structure of microbial communities. *Environ Microbiol* 16: 2659–2671.
- de Lorenzo, V. (2008) Systems biology approaches to bioremediation. *Curr Opin Biotechnol* 19: 579–589.
- de Lorenzo, V., Marliere, P., and Sole, R. (2016) Bioremediation at a global scale: from the test tube to planet Earth. *Microb Biotechnol* 9: 618–625.
- Mendes, L.W., Tsai, S.M., Navarrete, A.A., de Hollander, M., van Veen, J.A., and Kuramae, E.E. (2015) Soil-Borne Microbiome: Linking Diversity to Function. *Microb Ecol* 70: 255–265.
- Mesa, V., Gallego, J.L.R., González-gil, R., Lauga, B., Sánchez, J., Méndez-garcía, C., and Peláez, A.I. (2017) Bacterial, Archaeal, and Eukaryotic Diversity across Distinct Microhabitats in an Acid Mine Drainage. *Front Microbiol* 8: 1–17.
- Mühling, M., Poehlein, A., Stuhr, A., Voitel, M., Daniel, R., and Schlömann, M. (2016) Reconstruction of the metabolic potential of acidophilic sideroxydants strains from the metagenome of an microaerophilic enrichment culture of acidophilic iron-oxidizing bacteria from a pilot plant for the treatment of acid mine drainage reveals metabolic . *Front Microbiol* 7: 1–16.
- Mulligan, C.N. and Galvez-Cloutier, R. (2003) Bioremediation of metal contamination. *Environ Monit Assess* 84: 45–60.
- Neculita, C.M., Zagury, G.J., and Bussière, B. (2008) Effectiveness of sulfate-reducing passive bioreactors for treating highly contaminated acid mine drainage: II. Metal removal mechanisms and potential mobility. *Appl Geochemistry* 23: 3545–3560.

- Panigrahi, S., Velraj, P., and Subba Rao, T. (2019) Functional Microbial Diversity in Contaminated Environment and Application in Bioremediation, Elsevier Inc.
- Papirio, S., Villa-Gomez, D., Esposito, G., Pirozzi, F., and Lens, P.N.L. (2012) Acid mine drainage treatment in fluidized-bed bioreactors by sulfate-reducing bacteria: a critical review. *Crit Rev Environ Sci Technol* 22: 37–41.
- Pascale, J., Gwenneale, F., Quentin, Y., and Francois, D. (2002) Regulatory relationship of two-component and ABC transport systems and clustering of their genes in the Bacillus/Clostridium group, suggest a functional link between them. *J Mol Microbiol Biotechnol* 4: 503–513.
- Pereyra, L.P., Hiibel, S.R., Pruden, A., and Reardon, K.F. (2008) Comparison of microbial community composition and activity in sulfate-reducing batch systems remediating mine drainage. *Biotechnol Bioeng* 101: 702–713.
- Potrykus, J., Jonna, V. rao, and Dopson, M. (2011) Iron homeostasis and responses to iron limitation in extreme acidophiles from the Ferroplasma genus. *Proteomics* 11: 52–63.
- Pruden, A., Messner, N., Pereyra, L., Hanson, R.E., Hiibel, S.R., and Reardon, K.F. (2007) The effect of inoculum on the performance of sulfate-reducing columns treating heavy metal contaminated water. *Water Res* 41: 904–914.
- Robinson-Lora, M.A. and Brennan, R.A. (2011) Anaerobic precipitation of manganese and co-existing metals in mine impacted water treated with crab shell-associated minerals. *Appl Geochemistry* 26: 853–862.
- Robles-González, I. V., Fava, F., and Poggi-Varaldo, H.M. (2008) A review on slurry bioreactors for bioremediation of soils and sediments. *Microb Cell Fact* 7: 1–16.
- Roden, E.E. and Wetzel, R.G. (2003) Competition between Fe(III)-reducing and methanogenic bacteria for acetate in iron-rich freshwater sediments. *Microb Ecol* 45: 252–258.
- Sanabria, J. (2014) Environmental Biotechnology Research : Challenges and oportunitites in Latin America. *J Agric Env Ethics*.
- Sánchez-andrea, I., Luis, J., Bijmans, M.F.M., and Stams, A.J.M. (2014) Sulfate reduction at low pH to remediate acid mine drainage. *J Hazard Mater* 269: 98–109.
- Schwarz, W.H. (2001) The cellulosome and cellulose degradation by anaerobic bacteria. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 56: 634–649.
- Segata, N., Boernigen, D., Tickle, T.L., Morgan, X.C., Garrett, W.S., and Huttenhower, C. (2013) Computational meta'omics for microbial community studies. *Mol Syst Biol* 9: 666.
- Simate, G.S. and Ndlovu, S. (2014) Acid mine drainage: Challenges and opportunities. *J Environ Chem Eng* 2: 1785–1803.
- Solé, R. V., Montañez, R., and Duran-Nebreda, S. (2015) Synthetic circuit designs for earth terraformation. *Biol Direct* 10: 37.
- Song, H.-S., Cannon, W., Beliaev, A., and Konopka, A. (2014) Mathematical Modeling of Microbial Community Dynamics: A Methodological Review. *Processes* 2: 711–752.
- Suenaga, H. (2012) Targeted metagenomics: A high-resolution metagenomics approach for specific gene clusters in complex microbial communities. *Environ Microbiol* 14: 13–22.
- Sun, M., Xiao, T., Ning, Z., and Xiao, E. (2015) Microbial community analysis in rice paddy soils irrigated by acid mine drainage contaminated water. 2911–2922.
- Sun, W., Xiao, E., Krumins, V., Dong, Y., and Xiao, T. (2016) Characterization of the microbial community composition and the distribution of Fe-metabolizing bacteria in a creek contaminated by acid mine drainage. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol*.
- Sun, W., Xiao, T., Sun, M., Dong, Y., Ning, Z., Xiao, E., et al. (2015) Diversity of the Sediment Microbial Community in the Aha Watershed (Southwest China) in Response to Acid Mine Drainage. 81: 4874–4884.
- Techtman, S.M. and Hazen, T.C. (2016) Metagenomic applications in environmental monitoring and bioremediation. *J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol* 43: 1345–1354.
- Teng, W., Kuang, J., Luo, Z., and Shu, W. (2017) Microbial Diversity and Community Assembly across Environmental Gradients in Acid Mine Drainage. *Minerals* 7: 106.
- Thavamani, P., Samkumar, R.A., Satheesh, V., Subashchandrabose, S.R., Ramadass, K., Naidu, R., et al. (2017) Microbes from mined sites: Harnessing their potential for reclamation of derelict mine sites. *Environ Pollut* 230: 495–505.
- Ufarté, L., Laville, É., Duquesne, S., and Potocki-Veronese, G. (2015) Metagenomics for the discovery of pollutant degrading enzymes. *Biotechnol Adv* 33: 1845–1854.

- Vanwonterghem, I., Jensen, P.D., Ho, D.P., Batstone, D.J., and Tyson, G.W. (2014) Linking microbial community structure, interactions and function in anaerobic digesters using new molecular techniques. *Curr Opin Biotechnol* 27: 55–64.
- Vasquez, Y., Escobar, M.C., Saenz, J.S., Quiceno-Vallejo, M.F., Neculita, C.M., Arbeli, Z., and Roldan, F. (2018) Effect of hydraulic retention time on microbial community in biochemical passive reactors during treatment of acid mine drainage. *Bioresour Technol* 247: 624–632.
- Vilchez-Vargas, R., Junca, H., and Pieper, D.H. (2010) Metabolic networks, microbial ecology and “omics” technologies: Towards understanding in situ biodegradation processes. *Environ Microbiol* 12: 3089–3104.
- Wang, H., Guo, C.L., Yang, C.F., Lu, G.N., Chen, M.Q., and Dang, Z. (2016) Distribution and diversity of bacterial communities and sulphate-reducing bacteria in a paddy soil irrigated with acid mine drainage. *J Appl Microbiol* 121: 196–206.
- Wang, X. and Zhang, B. (2014) Integrating genomic, transcriptomic, and interactome data to improve peptide and protein identification in shotgun proteomics. *J Proteome Res* 13: 2715–2723.
- Xiao, S., Xie, X., and Liu, J. (2009) Microbial communities in acid water environments of two mines, China. *Environ Pollut* 157: 1045–1050.
- Xie, X., Xiao, S., and Liu, J. (2009) Microbial communities in acid mine drainage and their interaction with pyrite surface. *Curr Microbiol* 59: 71–77.
- Yang, Y., Li, Y., and Sun, Q.Y. (2014) Archaeal and bacterial communities in acid mine drainage from metal-rich abandoned tailing ponds, Tongling, China. *Trans Nonferrous Met Soc China (English Ed)* 24: 3332–3342.
- Yang, Y., Wan, M.X., Shi, W.Y., Peng, H., Qiu, G.Z., Zhou, J.Z., and Liu, X.D. (2007) Bacterial diversity and community structure in acid mine drainage from Dabaoshan Mine, China. *Aquat Microb Ecol* 47: 141–151.
- Zhao, Y.G., Wang, A.J., and Ren, N.Q. (2010) Effect of carbon sources on sulfidogenic bacterial communities during the starting-up of acidogenic sulfate-reducing bioreactors. *Bioresour Technol* 101: 2952–2959.
- Zhou, J., Xia, B., Treves, D.S., Wu, L.-Y., Marsh, T.L., O’Neill, R., et al. (2002) Spatial and Resource Factors Influencing High Microbial Diversity in Soil. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 68: 326–334.

CHAPTER II

On acid mine drainage detoxification: highly selected genes in microbiomes of biochemical passive reactors are enriched in two-component regulatory systems and ABC transporters

Marcela Villegas-Plazas^{1,2}, Janeth Sanabria¹, Ziv Arbeli³, Yaneth Vasquez⁴,
Fabio Roldan³, Howard Junca²

¹Environmental Microbiology and Biotechnology Laboratory, Engineering School of Environmental & Natural Resources, Engineering Faculty, Universidad del Valle, Cali, Colombia.

²RG Microbial Ecology: Metabolism, Genomics & Evolution, Div. Ecogenomics & Holobionts, Microbiomas Foundation, LT11A, 250008, Chia, Colombia.

³Unidad de Saneamiento y Biotecnología Ambiental USBA, Departamento de Biología, Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, Bogotá– Colombia.

⁴Departamento de Ciencias Naturales, Facultad de Ingeniería y Ciencias Básicas, Universidad Central, Carrera 5 No. 21-38, Bogotá, Colombia.

Abstract

Acid mine drainage (AMD) is the major pollutant generated by the mining industry and it is characterized by low pH and high concentration of metals and sulfate. As the use of biochemical passive reactors (BPRs) is a promising strategy for its bioremediation, in this work we characterized the dynamics of the microbiome assemblage and their inferred suprametabolism configuration in BPRs by 16S-amplicon and shotgun metagenomics sequencing. Our major findings were: 1) higher diversity of the microbiome was related to longer treatment times, 2) relative abundance of sulfate-reducing bacteria increased over time, 3) disproportionation of sulfur intermediates was high during efficient intervals, 4) AMD-presence was associated with increased frequency of genes encoding for two-component regulatory systems and ABC transporters, and 5) cellulose degradation was detected at increased frequency. Our results provide details on how complex microbial communities are adapted to grow in the presence of AMD.

Keywords

Acid mine drainage, bioremediation, biochemical passive reactors, metagenomics, functional adaptation, gene frequency, microbiome, suprametabolism.

Disclaimer: A different version of the following content was submitted in:
Environmental Pollution (ISSN:0269-7491)

2.1 Introduction

Acid mine drainage (AMD) is the major type of contaminated effluent generated by the mining industry (Akciil and Koldas, 2006; Nordstrom, 2019) impacting key terrestrial biomes all over the world (Sonter *et al.*, 2018). It is characterized by low pH and high concentration of metals and sulfate (Chen *et al.*, 2016). As this type of waste has a serious impact on human health and ecosystems (Landrigan *et al.*, 2018), its control, containment and treatment are some of the main environmental challenges (Jennings *et al.*, 2008).

Among the remediation technologies to cope with this issue Biochemical Passive Reactors (BPRs) are a promising sustainable and safer alternative (Johnson and Hallberg, 2005; Fitch, 2015). They consist of columns filled with a reactive mixture composed of organic and inorganic substrates and their microbiological load, through which the flowing AMD is neutralized and metals are removed or modified to less toxic states (Johnson *et al.*, 2002; Jong and Parry, 2003). The effectiveness of bioremediation in BPRs relies on the engineering of essential design parameters such as hydraulic retention time (HRT) and the composition of the reactive mixture as conditioning substrate promoting, but also on the dynamics of selecting bacteria playing the desired biochemical reactions (Aoyagi *et al.*, 2017). Further comparative and comprehensive inferences to improve the understanding of these dynamics can be performed through high-throughput DNA sequencing technologies (Villegas-Plazas *et al.*, 2019). The characterization of microbiomes through the integration of these multidisciplinary approaches has reinforced the concept of microbial communities as complex adaptive systems that can bioremediate pollutants by a network of spatially distributed interactive agents, both in enclosed engineered systems and open environments (Burow *et al.*, 2019; Lukhele *et al.*, 2019; Villegas-Plazas *et al.*, 2019).

Under anaerobic conditions, sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB) oxidize low molecular carbon sources using sulfate as final electron acceptor, producing hydrogen sulfides and increasing pH (Jong and Parry, 2003). Sulfides react with dissolved metals, precipitating them in compounds of very low solubility (Aoyagi *et al.*, 2017). Simultaneously, the low molecular carbon sources required for sulfate reduction are produced by the microbial community through degradation and fermentation of more complex compounds such as cellulose and diverse polysaccharides, which are provided in the reactive mixture to increase the useful service-life of BPRs.

Given the need to improve the overall understanding of AMD bioremediation treatments, we selected BPRs as study model in which predicted functions out of taxonomical microbiome composition can be compared to the functions directly inferred by extensive shotgun metagenomics analyses, retrieved from the same experimental sampling setup. In this article we report the comparison of the shifts of the microbial diversity, variations of the inferred functional potential, and associated gene abundances over treatment time. This allowed us to identify key variations contributing to the establishment of an AMD resilient microbial community, and detecting as a proxy of gene frequencies over the metagenome, the functional content categories that are increasing in metagenomes. Excluding central metabolism, genes rising in the BPR treating AMD are either those genes of well-defined putative functions already inferred from abundant ribotypes and reference genomes in such systems, but notably, also novel genes categorized in transport and sensing functional categories. The possible interpretations of those genes of higher fitness in this system are presented and discussed.

2.2 Experimental Procedures

2.2.1 Samples source

16S data and samples for shotgun-metagenome sequencing were obtained from laboratory-scale assays of BPRs (Vasquez et al., 2016a; Vasquez et al., 2016b; Vasquez et al., 2018) consisting of seven 5 L reactors operated at 3 different hydraulic retention time (HRT 1, 2 and 4 days) filled with a reactive mixture [15% cow manure, 10% mushroom compost, 25% sawdust, 15% gravel, 20% limestone, and 15% wetland sediment as inoculum (dry weight in % w/w)] and fed from the bottom with synthetic AMD [$201 \pm 44 \text{ Fe}^{2+}$; $30 \pm 2 \text{ Mn}^{2+}$; $19 \pm 2 \text{ Zn}^{2+}$; $215 \pm 11 \text{ Ca}^{2+}$; $128 \pm 13 \text{ Mg}^{2+}$ and $2500 \pm 105 \text{ SO}_4^{2-}$ (in mg L⁻¹); pH 3.0- 3.7]. In this study we selected the 2 days HRT reactors that represent three different treatment times (8, 17 and 36 weeks), coupling 16S information and shotgun metagenomics sequencing and annotation (Supplementary Figure 1). Set-up and operation details of BPRs were previously reported (Vasquez et al., 2016b).

2.2.2 Characterization of the microbial community structure

The raw sequencing data of the 16S rRNA gene amplicon (hypervariable region V4) Illumina sequencing accounting for approximately 1.3 million reads from a total of 28 samples were used for analyses, interpretation and comparisons detailed below. The 28 samples represented triplicate of three reactor sections (top, middle, and bottom) at 3 different treatment times (8, 17 and 36 weeks) and an additional sample from the original reactive mixture (0 weeks).

Processing of sequencing reads was conducted by using Qiime2 (version 2019.1) (Hall and Beiko, 2018); denoising, quality filtering and chimera checking (“consensus”) were performed by the ‘dada2’ plugin (Callahan et al., 2016), collapsing reads into 5,874 amplicon sequence variants (ASVs). Taxonomy of these ASVs was assigned against the SILVA database (132 released; 2018) using the ‘fit-classifier-sklearn’ plugin (<https://docs.qiime2.org/2019.1/plugins/available/feature-classifier/classify-sklearn/>). Alpha and beta diversity analyses were performed using ‘phyloseq’ package (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013). ASVs co-occurrence analysis was performed with default packages in R, and Cytoscape (v. 3.7.2) software was used to visualize the network graphs.

2.2.3 Whole shotgun metagenome sequencing and analyses

2.2.3.1 Metagenomic DNA extraction and sequencing

Samples collected from the AMD-input section (bottom) were selected for functional inferences by in depth shotgun metagenomics. The microbial communities at this point are the first ones exposed in the BPRs to the AMD, and are the first in the system to perform biological transformations, while in the middle and top sections physical-chemical reactions and undetermined secondary effects and activities such as crossfeeding of the metabolites, or biomass produced in the first section may interfere direct interpretations. Distinct features in the composition of microbial communities in the bioreactors from our previous studies provided additional insights about the bottom section as a most suitable for the functional characterization by metagenomics. This layer is the taxonomically most diverse section in terms of abundance and richness of bacterial types detected, and it has the highest relative abundance of bacteria related to sulfate reduction and

iron metabolism. Metagenomic DNA was extracted using the commercial kit NucleoSpin Soil (Macherey-Nagel GmbH, Germany). Each sample was divided into six 1 g-subsamples that were subject to lysis using 700 μ L of lysis buffer SL1 and 10 μ L of Enhancer SX. Vortex was applied to each subsample in a NucleoSpin bead tube at maximum speed for 5 minutes and then samples were subjected to orbital shaker agitation at 200 rpm for 3 hours. The six lysed subsamples were joined into one and then the NucleoSpin Soil Kit protocol was followed according to manufacturer's instructions. Metagenomic DNA was eluted in 50 μ L of elution buffer SE and quantified using Qubit (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc, USA). Sequencing was performed using HiSeq-Illumina4000 2x150bp by ABM Inc (Vancouver, Canada). Data has been deposited in MG-RAST under accession numbers mgm4839714.3, mgm4839715.3, and mgm4839716.3; and raw data can be also found in the European Nucleotide Archive under the project accession number PRJEB31837.

2.2.3.2 *Metagenome assembly and gene annotation*

Illumina adapters were removed and reads were filter based on their quality (Q30) and length using Trimmomatic (v. 0.38) (Bolger et al., 2014). A primary set of contigs was generated for each sample individually with MEGAHIT (v. 1.2.9) (Li et al., 2016) using a k-mer length of 141 and a minimal contig length of 200bp. Under the same conditions, a secondary set of contigs was generated co-assembling the reads from the three samples. Gene prediction was performed on the assembled contigs using Prokka (Seemann, 2014) and functional annotation was achieved through EggNOG database (Huerta-cepas et al., 2016).

2.2.3.3 *Frequency abundance determination of each ORF*

BBMap (<https://sourceforge.net/projects/bbmap/>) and samtools (Li et al., 2009) were used to calculate the read coverage per predicted ORF; this process was performed both in the set of contigs generated for each sample individually and those from the co-assembly process, obtained as a result the average fold coverage of each ORF during the three treatment times (8, 17 and 36 weeks). Before that, the three datasets were normalized by equaling the number of reads using deepTools2 (Ramírez et al., 2016).

2.2.3.4 *Statistical Analysis*

Multivariate data analysis was used to explore and test abundance profiles of genes and taxa across the variables, all analyses were performed using R 3.4.3. For the taxonomic structure of the communities, the experimental design was set up as a two-way crossed design with time and reactor section, and the differences between the genera were evaluated using the two-way permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA), which were considered significantly different if the p value fell < 0.01 . Changes in the supra-metabolism of the communities across treatment times were analyzed using ANOVA. Multiple comparison corrections were made using Benjamini-Hochberg. Significant differences in the relative abundance of COGs, KOs and genes (average fold coverage) were considered if the p value fell < 0.01 .

For co-occurrence network inference, all Spearman's rank correlations between ASVs were calculated using R 3.4.3. Significant taxon co-occurrence were considered if Spearman rank coefficient was > 0.8 and statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) (Barberán et al., 2011). Cytoscape (v. 3.7.2) software was used to visualize the network graphs.

2.3 Results and Discussion

Biochemical passive reactors (BPRs) have emerged as a biotechnological alternative to treat AMD; they are efficient systems performing specific processes such as pollutant transformation, and they are also an interesting case study of microbial community adaptation to strong selective pressures such as AMD. In this study, that follows up previous works (Vasquez et al., 2016a; Vasquez et al., 2016b; Vasquez et al., 2018), microbiomes of three laboratory-scale BPR representing different treatment times (8, 16 and, 36 weeks) during AMD bioremediation were analyzed in detail. Our results provided a snapshot of the progressive adaptation of these microbial communities to the constant input of AMD, resulted in an increased sulfate reduction rate (52%) and metal removal (99%), which achieved the highest values by the end of the study (36 weeks) (Vasquez et al., 2016a). The characterization of BPR's microbiomes was performed through metagenomics, analyzing the taxonomic composition, their functional predicted content and the collective metabolism annotation and interpretation.

2.3.1 Determining the structure and composition of microbial communities from BPR

A total of 1.135.142 reads were assigned to 5.874 ASVs after quality filter and chimera checking implemented in DADA2, showing all samples similarly high level of saturation of ASVs richness. Patterns of species richness (observed species and Chao1), evenness scores and alpha-diversity (Shannon) revealed variability between communities with an increase in the number of species across the treatment time, suggesting that diversity may enhance the robustness of BPRs and could be positively correlated with their improved performance.

More than 60 microbial phyla and 307 genera, including 6 different Archaea lineages were derived from these communities; Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes, and Firmicutes were dominant in all samples accounting together for 60% to 70% of the total taxon abundance (Supplementary Figure 1). Greater diversity and accumulation at the bottom section of genera related with key steps in sulfur and iron metabolism, such as *Desulfatiglans*, *Desulfovira*, *Magnetobacterium*, *Desulfobacca*, *Syntrophorhabdus*, and *Desulfobacterium* (Figure 1) evidenced that the sulfate concentration ($2500 \pm 170 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) in the synthetic AMD used in these experiments did not negatively influence the structure of microbial communities, but, to the contrary, led to the growth of specialized species. Dynamics in the microbiomes' composition indicated that the bottom section of the BPRs was already harboring a selected and stably maintained microbial community with functional potential to play the desired biochemical transformations.

Significant taxon co-occurrence was explored through a network analysis. The BPRs microbiome network of positive relationships between genera was comprised by 207 nodes and 1.580 edges visualized among three densely connected modules (Figure 2A), in which most of them occurred at the intra-phyla level, especially for Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes and Firmicutes. These type of interactions may be assembling random associations or may be suggesting synergetic relationships (Barberán et al., 2011). To discern that, a categorization based on the metabolic and physiological information available for all genera was produced (Figure 2B). The three major modules of highly interacting genera showed the sugar fermenters and cellulose degraders as key components, sharing multiple interactions between them and bacteria performing anaerobic respiration using S^0 , NO_3 and Fe (III) as terminal electron acceptors. This was a crucial relationship inside the BPRs, because they produce from the complex organic matter of the reactive mixture, small

molecules that are needed by those as the SRB. Module 1 confirmed the association of genera of sulfur and iron metabolism, evidencing similar responses to abiotic parameters, such as the accumulation of sulfate and sulfide-metal compounds, and interconnected metabolism.

Figure 1. A) Species richness and alpha-diversity of all samples, differentiating by treatment time and reactor section. B) Relative frequency of genera with significant differences between treatment time and reactor section. C) Summarizing two-way crossed ANOVA data for genera with p value < 0.01.

Figure 2. A) Significant taxon co-occurrence revealing three major modules of correlations inside the BPRs microbiomes. B) Distributions of metabolisms previously described for the genera composing each one of the modules.

2.3.2 Supra-metabolism characterization through metagenomics

More than 16GB of raw data were generated using Hiseq4000-Illumina pair-end sequencing from bottom section samples (see rationale in Experimental Procedures 2.2.3.1) of the three BPR representing AMD-treatment times of 8, 17 and 36 weeks. After quality filtering, approximately 4GB of clean paired data per sample were obtained and resulted in 1.545.407 redundant ORFs (Supplementary Table 1).

Figure 3 is showing the profile in Cluster of Orthologous Groups (COG) of the communities obtained from Egnog annotation; 25-30% of the ORFs were unclassified or have unknown functions. Comparing the communities at this level, uniformity in the central pathways necessary to maintain the basic cellular machinery was evidenced. 10.314 ORFs presented highly significant differences between the samples, most of them increasing their average fold coverage across treatment times. Among those, 34% corresponded to metabolic categories, 23% to cellular processes, 14% to information storage and processing types, and the rest of them were of currently unassigned and poorly characterized functions (Supplementary Table 3).

Figure 3. Relative abundance of COG in each sample, according the average fold coverage.

2.3.3 Carbon metabolism

Functions of peripheral cellulose degradation, along with the first two stages of the glycolytic pathway were the most abundant in samples from longer treatment times (Figure 4A), suggesting that more cellulose and complex polysaccharides were degraded to produce simple carbon sources that can be used by SBR. There was also evidence for increased frequency of autotrophic CO₂ fixation via the reductive tricarboxylic acid cycle (Figure 4B), which results also in the production of a variety of low molecular carbon sources, such as pyruvate, oxaloacetate, and fumarate. This CO₂ assimilation pathway can be associated to the genera

Methanobacterium, *Acetobacterium* (Shiba et al., 1985), *Chlorobium* (Wahlund and Tabita, 1997), and *Nitrospira* (Poghosyan et al., 2019), which were present in these communities. There are also reports about autotrophic SRB from the genera *Desulfobacter*, *Desulfobacterium* and *Desulfovibrio* performing this metabolic route in the presence of acetate (Hansen and Hansen, 1993). All the ASVs associated to these genera had a greater relative abundance at the bottom sections and increased during the treatment time.

SRB can present complete or incomplete oxidation of organic compounds, but most of them perform partial interrupted pathways which result in the excretion of acetate as the main product (Agostino et al., 2018). This substrate has been reported as the preferred organic compound for Fe(III)-reducing and methanogenic microorganisms, and their competition for this metabolite is one of the main limiting factors attributed to the suppression of methanogenesis in iron or sulfate rich environments (Roden and Wetzel, 2003). Our metagenomic results identified acetate oxidation as one of the over time increased functions, indicating growth of Fe (III) reducing bacteria in synergy with SRB performing incomplete oxidation of organic substrate. This is supported not only by the high frequency of *pta* and *ackA* genes, but also by the distribution pattern of these type of bacteria (Figure 1B) and their co-occurrence (Figure 2B).

Figure 4. Frequency of main reactions in A) cellulose degradation and B) the reductive tricarboxylic acid cycle for each sample, represented in log₁₀ of the average fold coverage.

2.3.4 Membrane Transport

Survival of microbial communities in extreme environmental conditions is heavily relying on their ability to quickly detect and respond to specific abiotic factors, which generally depends on the capacity to mobilize a wide variety of compounds across biological membranes (Pascale et al., 2002). Multiple genes putatively encoding Two-Component Systems (TCS) and ATP binding cassettes (ABC Transporters) were detected with an increased frequency across the treatment time (Figure 5), triggering the community to an adaptative process, and especially those related to the mobilization of metals and inorganic ions, which are fundamental parts of the metabolic system that promote microbial resistance to toxic metals (Lovley et al., 2004). On the other hand, patterns observed for genes involved in the mobilization of products of cellulose degradation, such as cellobiose and simple sugars coincide with the results exposed above (Figure 4A).

Figure 5. Comparative abundance of genes coding for specific Two-component systems and ABC Transports in each sample, represented in log₁₀ of the average fold coverage.

2.3.5 Oxidative phosphorylation and energy metabolism

Figure 6 is showing the shifts in the frequency of genes encoding assimilatory and dissimilatory sulfate reduction, evidencing that all reactions in both pathways increased synchronically their frequencies. A remarkable feature of these data was the fact that together with the sulfite production via assimilatory pathway, the dissimilatory sulfite reduction by the complex of anaerobic sulfite reductase shown an increased pattern, suggesting also the presence of disproportionation of sulfur intermediates, which is the use of sulfite or thiosulfate as a final electron acceptor for the generation of hydrogen sulfide (Finster, 2008). Other activities inside the sulfur cycle, such as sulfur-oxidizing and DMSO metabolism had a constant but lower relative abundance in all samples.

Nitrate is one of the most common electron acceptors in anaerobic metabolism, as it has a higher redox potential than sulfate, its metabolism is more energy-efficient. *Nar*, *Nas* and *Nir* genes involved in assimilatory and dissimilatory nitrate reduction were present with greater abundance in the early stages of the AMD treatment, but their average fold coverage decreased over time, possibly due to the exhaustion of the substrate. Meanwhile, nitrogen fixation-associated genes increased their relative abundance, suggesting that this function might have an important implication for the overall bioremediation function and biomass balance inside the BPRs. Nitrogen fixation, when is associated to an inorganic molecule as final electron acceptor, must be coupled to energy production by oxidative phosphorylation, which implies an electron transport chain supported by periplasmatic enzymes such as cytochromes. As an addition supporting insight, microbial communities from these BPR system showed a time-increased frequency of genes

associated to these complexes and an augmented abundance of F-type ATPases compared to the vacuolar-type.

Figure 6. Frequency of each reaction in assimilatory and dissimilatory sulfate reduction for each sample, represented in $\log_{10}$ of the average fold coverage.

2.4 Conclusions

This study used an integrative perspective to characterize the dynamics of the microbiomes inside bioreactors treating AMD, and identified shifts in the species composition and gene abundance that led the community to an adaptive process to a more effective transformation of the pollutant. Some of the outstanding findings were: (1) greater species richness diversity across treatment time, (2) synergy between SRB and Fe(III) reducing bacteria, (3) a higher frequency of genes associated to Two-component systems and ABC transporters, and (4) co-selected increment of cellulose degradation, sugar fermentation and sulfur and iron metabolism.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the financial support from Departamento Administrativo de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación – COLCIENCIAS – through doctoral fellowship “Beca de Estudios Doctorales Nacionales 727 granted to M. Villegas-Plazas and the access to computing infrastructure kindly provided by Prof Ericsson Coy Ph.D. INQUIBIO-UMNG.

2.5 References

- Agostino, V., Rosenbaum, M.A., Lorenzo, M. Di, 2018. Sulfate-Reducing Electro Autotrophs and Their Applications in Bioelectrochemical Systems. *Front. Energy Res.* 6, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2018.00055>
- Akcil, A., Koldas, S., 2006. Acid Mine Drainage (AMD): causes , treatment and case studies 14, 1139–1145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2004.09.006>
- Aoyagi, T., Hamai, T., Hori, T., Sato, Yuki, Kobayashi, M., Sato, Yuya, Inaba, T., Ogata, A., Habe, H., Sakata, T., 2017. Hydraulic retention time and pH affect the performance and microbial communities of passive bioreactors for treatment of acid mine drainage. *AMB Express* 7, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13568-017-0440-z>
- Barberán, A., Bates, S.T., Casamayor, E.O., Fierer, N., 2011. Using network analysis to explore co-occurrence patterns in soil microbial communities. *ISME J.* 6, 343–351. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2011.119>
- Bolger, A.M., Lohse, M., Usadel, B., 2014. Genome analysis Trimmomatic : a flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data 30, 2114–2120. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu170>
- Burow, K., Grawunder, A., Harpke, M., Pietschmann, S., Ehrhardt, R., Wagner, L., Voigt, K., Merten, D., Büchel, G., Kothe, E., 2019. Microbiomes in an acidic rock-water cave system. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* 366, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsle/fnz167>
- Callahan, B.J., Mcmurdie, P.J., Rosen, M.J., Han, A.W., Johnson, A.J.A., Holmes, S.P., 2016. DADA2 : High-resolution sample inference from Illumina amplicon data 13, 581–587. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.3869>
- Chen, L. xing, Huang, L. nan, Méndez-García, C., Kuang, J. liang, Hua, Z. shuang, Liu, J., Shu, W. sheng, 2016. Microbial communities, processes and functions in acid mine drainage ecosystems. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* 38, 150–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copbio.2016.01.013>
- Finster, K., 2008. Microbiological disproportionation of inorganic sulfur compounds. *J. Sulfur Chem.* 29, 281–292. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17415990802105770>
- Fitch, M., 2015. Mine-Impacted Water and Biochemical Reactors, Food, Energy, and Water: The Chemistry Connection. Elsevier Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-800211-7.00005-3>
- Hall, M., Beiko, R.G., 2018. 16 rRNA Gene Analysis with QIIME2 1849, 113–129.
- Hansen, Theo A, Hansen, Thea A, 1993. Carbon Metabolism of Sulfate-Reducing Bacteria.
- Huerta-cepas, J., Szklarczyk, D., Forslund, K., Cook, H., Heller, D., Walter, M.C., Rattei, T., Mende, D.R., Sunagawa, S., Kuhn, M., Jensen, L.J., Mering, C. Von, 2016. eggNOG 4 . 5: a hierarchical orthology framework with improved functional annotations for eukaryotic, prokaryotic and viral sequences. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 44, 286–293. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv1248>
- Jennings, S.R., Blicher, S., Neuman, P., Dennis, R., 2008. Acid mine drainage and effects on fish health and ecology: a review. *Reclam. Res. Gr.* 1, 1–26.
- Johnson, D.B., Hallberg, K.B., 2005. Acid mine drainage remediation options: A review. *Sci. Total Environ.* 338, 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2004.09.002>
- Jong, T., Parry, D.L., 2003. Removal of sulfate and heavy metals by sulfate reducing bacteria in short-term bench scale upflow anaerobic packed bed reactor runs. *Water Res.* 37, 3379–3389. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(03\)00165-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(03)00165-9)
- Landrigan, P.J., Fuller, R., Acosta, N.J.R., Adeyi, O., Arnold, R., Basu, N. (Nil), Baldé, A.B., Bertollini, R., Bose-O'Reilly, S., Boufford, J.I., Breyse, P.N., Chiles, T., Mahidol, C., Coll-Seck, A.M., Cropper, M.L., Fobil, J., Fuster, V., Greenstone, M., Haines, A., Hanrahan, D., Hunter, D., Khare, M., Krupnick, A., Lanphear, B., Lohani, B., Martin, K., Mathiasen, K. V., McTeer, M.A., Murray, C.J.L., Ndahimananjara, J.D., Perera, F., Potočník, J., Preker, A.S., Ramesh, J., Rockström, J., Salinas, C., Samson, L.D., Sandilya, K., Sly, P.D., Smith, K.R., Steiner, A., Stewart, R.B., Suk, W.A., van Schayck, O.C.P., Yadama, G.N., Yumkella, K., Zhong, M., 2018. The Lancet Commission on pollution and health. *Lancet* 391, 462–512. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)32345-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)32345-0)
- Li, D., Luo, R., Liu, C.M., Leung, C.M., Ting, H.F., Sadakane, K., Yamashita, H., Lam, T.W., 2016. MEGAHIT v1.0: A fast and scalable metagenome assembler driven by advanced methodologies and community practices. *Methods* 102, 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymeth.2016.02.020>
- Li, H., Handsaker, B., Wysoker, A., Fennell, T., Ruan, J., Homer, N., Marth, G., Abecasis, G., Durbin, R., 2009. The Sequence Alignment/Map format and SAMtools. *Bioinformatics* 25, 2078–2079. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btp352>
- Lovley, D.R., Holmes, D.E., Nevin, K.P., 2004. Dissimilatory Fe(III) and Mn(IV) reduction. *Adv. Microb. Physiol.* 49, 219–286. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2911\(04\)49005-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2911(04)49005-5)
- Lukhele, T., Selvarajan, R., Nyoni, H., Mamba, B.B., Msagati, T.A.M., 2019. Acid Mine Drainage as Habitats for Distinct Microbiomes: Current Knowledge in the Era of Molecular and Omic Technologies. *Curr. Microbiol.*

- <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00284-019-01771-z>
- McMurdie, P.J., Holmes, S., 2013. phyloseq: an R package for reproducible interactive analysis and graphics of microbiome census data. *PLoS One* 8, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0061217>
- Nordstrom, D.K., 2019. Geochemical modelling for mine site characterization and remediation. *E3S Web Conf.* 98, 4–8. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/20199805013>
- Pascale, J., Gwenneale, F., Quentin, Y., Francois, D., 2002. Regulatory relationship of two-component and ABC transport systems and clustering of their genes in the *Bacillus/Clostridium* group, suggest a functional link between them. *J Mol Microbiol Biotechnol* 4, 503–513.
- Poghosyan, L., Koch, H., Lavy, A., Frank, J., Kessel, M.A.H.J. Van, Jetten, M.S.M., Ban, J.F., Lückner, S., 2019. Metagenomic recovery of two distinct comammox *Nitrospira* from the terrestrial subsurface 21, 3627–3637. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1462-2920.14691>
- Ramírez, F., Ryan, D.P., Grüning, B., Bhardwaj, V., Kilpert, F., Richter, A.S., Heyne, S., Dündar, F., Manke, T., 2016. deepTools2: a next generation web server for deep-sequencing data analysis. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 44, W160–W165. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkw257>
- Roden, E.E., Wetzel, R.G., 2003. Competition between Fe(III)-reducing and methanogenic bacteria for acetate in iron-rich freshwater sediments. *Microb. Ecol.* 45, 252–258. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-002-1037-9>
- Seemann, T., 2014. Prokka: rapid prokaryotic genome annotation 30, 2068–2069. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu153>
- Shiba, H., Kawasumi, T., Igarashi, Y., Kodama, T., Minoda, Y., 1985. The CO₂ assimilation via the reductive tricarboxylic acid cycle in an obligately autotrophic, aerobic hydrogen-oxidizing bacterium, *Hydrogenobacter thermophilus*. *Arch Microbiol.* 12695, 198–203.
- Sonter, L.J., Ali, S.H., Watson, J.E.M., 2018. Mining and biodiversity: Key issues and research needs in conservation science. *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 285, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2018.1926>
- Vasquez, Y., Escobar, M.C., Neculita, C.M., Arbeli, Z., Roldan, F., 2016a. Biochemical passive reactors for treatment of acid mine drainage: Effect of hydraulic retention time on changes in efficiency, composition of reactive mixture, and microbial activity. *Chemosphere* 153, 244–253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.03.052>
- Vasquez, Y., Escobar, M.C., Neculita, C.M., Arbeli, Z., Roldan, F., 2016b. Selection of reactive mixture for biochemical passive treatment of acid mine drainage. *Environ. Earth Sci.* 75, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-016-5374-2>
- Vasquez, Y., Escobar, M.C., Saenz, J.S., Quiceno-Vallejo, M.F., Neculita, C.M., Arbeli, Z., Roldan, F., 2018. Effect of hydraulic retention time on microbial community in biochemical passive reactors during treatment of acid mine drainage. *Bioresour. Technol.* 247, 624–632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.09.144>
- Villegas-Plazas, M., Sanabria, J., Junca, H., 2019. A composite taxonomical and functional framework of microbiomes under acid mine drainage bioremediation systems. *J. Environ. Manage.* 251, 109581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.109581>
- Wahlund, T.M., Tabita, F.R., 1997. The Reductive Tricarboxylic Acid Cycle of Carbon Dioxide Assimilation : Initial Studies and Purification of ATP-Citrate Lyase from the Green Sulfur Bacterium *Chlorobium tepidum* 179, 4859–4867.

CHAPTER III

Evaluation of a promiscuous conjugative plasmid (*pMating221*) as a plausible gene mobilization tool for genetic bioaugmentation of environmental bacteria

Marcela Villegas-Plazas^{1,2*}, Elena Algar³, Janeth Sanabria²,
Howard Junca¹, Víctor de Lorenzo³

¹RG Microbial Ecology: Metabolism, Genomics & Evolution, Div. Ecogenomics & Holobionts, Microbiomas Foundation, LT11A, 250008, Chia, Colombia.

²Environmental Microbiology and Biotechnology Laboratory, Engineering School of Environmental & Natural Resources, Engineering Faculty, Universidad del Valle, Cali, Colombia.

³Systems Biology Department, Centro Nacional de Biotecnología (CNB-CSIC), Campus de Cantoblanco, Madrid, 28049 Spain.

Abstract

Bioremediation is considered an essential activity to restore the planet to a sustainable state, therefore, the research of strategies to improve its efficiency has become a priority in the field of environmental sciences, such as the design of bioreactors, *in-situ* biostimulation or bioaugmentation. The bioaugmentation mediated by plasmids to transfer and spread metabolic functions inside complex microbial communities of soils, water, or engineering ecosystems, has emerged as a promising tool for improving pollutant transformation. This study investigated the properties of the modular plasmid *pMating221* to be taken from the media by natural competent cells, and to be self-transmissible between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria isolated from soils impacted with acid mine drainage (AMD). Our experiments demonstrated that *pMating221* works under aerobic and anaerobic conditions and has a broad host range of transformation and conjugal transference. It was incorporated to strains from the genera *Aeromonas*, *Bacillus* and *Cellulosimicrobium*, and also “*trans*-Gram conjugated” between them. These results confirm *pMating221* as a promising tool approach for genetic bioaugmentation in microbiomes for experiments prone to be scaled-up in microcosms. Additionally, we are presenting the design proposal of three different accessory modules to be introduced inside the vector of the specific variants’ genes showing increased frequency inside microbial communities performing AMD bioremediation.

Keywords: Genetic Bioaugmentation, Conjugative Plasmid, Bioremediation, Anaerobiosis

3.1 Introduction

Acid mine drainage (AMD) is the major waste generated by the mining industry (Akcil and Koldas, 2006; Nordstrom, 2019) and it has serious impact on human health and ecosystem (Landrigan *et al.*, 2018). Its control, containment and treatment has become a great concern for the current challenge of restoring the Earth to a sustainable state. Biotechnology has played an important role in the development of eco-friendly bioremediation strategies, such as Biochemical Passive Reactors. These systems have turned out to be a promising strategy because they required minimal operation and use microorganisms in complex and dynamic communities, in which multiples interconnected networks of metabolic and ecological interactions provide the process with greater robustness and efficient advantages, such as division of labor (Hays *et al.*, 2015).

Beside the engineering of essential design parameters, performing of passive reactors can be improved through biological strategies such as bioaugmentation, which consists in the introduction of novel metabolic functions into microbial communities, often done by addition of isolated strains with specific abilities (Bathe *et al.*, 2004). However, multiple studies have reported that the added microorganisms are not often able to adapt to the new environments, due to abiotic stress and ecological competition with the local microbial community (Bathe *et al.*, 2004; Zhang *et al.*, 2012). A recent proposal to cope with this issue has been the bioaugmentation mediated not by cells but by mobile genetic elements, which could spread specific genes inside the complex microbial community (Garbisu *et al.*, 2017).

Most common mobile genetic elements include plasmids, transposons, virus, and insertion sequences; between them, conjugative plasmids have been recognized as the most impactful mechanisms for horizontal gene transfer. These elements, also called self-transmissible plasmids contain a backbone with several comprehensive genetic features to enhance their maintenance and mobility within the community (Pinilla-redondo *et al.*, 2018); with additional accessory modules that give to the host selective advantages such as resistance to antibiotics, heavy metals or specific metabolic abilities (Springael and Top, 2004). The horizontal gene transfer is mediated by three different mechanisms: transformation which is the uptake of DNA from the environment; transduction that is the transfer of DNA via phage vector; and conjugation that involves direct cell-to-cell contact to mobilize DNA between bacteria (Harrison and Brockhurst, 2012). Compare to cell bioaugmentation, genetic bioaugmentation through a conjugative plasmid could be a more effective strategy to improve bioremediation, by the fact that native bacteria hosting the new metabolic abilities are expected to be already adapted to the polluted environment and the co-occurred taxa (Garbisu *et al.*, 2017).

The aim of this study was to investigate the ability of the conjugative plasmid *pMating221* to transform bacteria that were isolated from AMD water and impacted soils, evaluating if it can be used as a tool to generate a massive horizontal gene transfer and improve AMD-bioremediation systems. At the end of the study, the plasmid could be introduced in both, aerobic and anaerobic bacteria via transformation and transconjugation activity, suggesting potential attributes for the implementation of the genetic bioaugmentation strategy. Based on that, we are presenting the proposal of three new modules to insert inside the plasmid *pMating221* extra specific genes involved in the metabolism of acid mine drainage; those genes were identified as genes of increased frequency during efficient AMD bioremediation (Chapter 2).

3.2 Materials and Methods-

3.2.1 Plasmid concept and design

pMating221 is a conjugative plasmid of ~24K designed at Molecular Environmental Microbiology Laboratory, CNB, CSIC. It is a low-copy-number vector containing the origin of replication of RK2 (oriV), kanamycin resistance and two distinct regions designated Tra1 and Tra2 encoding essential functions to conjugation. To facilitate the identification of transformant colonies, a new gadget containing the flavin mononucleotide-based fluorescent protein (EcFbFP) with the moderate promoter BG25 (Zobel et al., 2015) and the transcriptional terminator T500 (Martínez-García et al., 2014) was introduced inside the vector. This protein was selected because acts as an oxygen-independent reported, fluorescing in both aerobic and anaerobic environments (Drepper et al., 2007; Tielker et al., 2009). EcFbFP emits strong fluorescence at 495 nm upon excitation with blue light (450 nm) (Nikel and de Lorenzo, 2013) (Figure 1).

The construction of the gadget was achieved with 4 serial PCR reactions using in each one of them two different templates with overlapping ends. The set of primers was designed following the same strategy of Gibson assembly, adding to the primers two overlapping tails with the fragment adjacent to each end. *SanDI* and *SwaI* restrictions sequences were respectively added to 5' and 3' to insert the gadget inside the vector pMating221.

3.2.2 Bacterial isolation from AMD-impacted soils

AMD water and three samples of soil highly impacted with AMD from a coal mine located in Samacá, Boyacá (Colombia) were collected with sterile spoons, preserved into clean bags and stored at 4 °C until lab processing. Two different methods were used to isolate bacteria from those samples, direct spreading and liquid pre-incubation method. For direct spreading method, 1g of soil sample or 1 mL of AMD water were mixed with 0.75% NaCl solution and vortexed for 3 minutes; serial dilutions were performed, and 100 µL of 10² to 10⁶ were spread directly onto the surface of Luria Bertani (LB), LB 1/10, and Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) agar media. Cultures in LB were incubated under aerobic conditions at 30°C for 2-3 days, while BHI agar media cultures were incubated under anaerobic conditions (GasPak™, H₂+CO₂) at 30 °C for 5- 8 days.

For the liquid pre-incubation method, 1 g of soil or 1 mL of AMD water was inoculated in 9 mL of LB 1/10 and BHI broth, and then incubated under aerobic and anaerobic conditions, respectively, at 30 °C for 2 – 5 days. After incubation, each culture was diluted and spread onto the same agar media and incubated as specified above. All the colonies with different morphotypes were purified and tested with Gram stain, catalase, and kanamycin resistance; those that were naturally resistant to this antibiotic were discarded for further experiments.

Figure 1. Module architecture of plasmid *pMating221*

3.2.3 Evaluation of *pMating221*-transformation of aerobic isolates

Aerobic strains were cultured in 5 mL of LB broth and incubated overnight at 37 °C, 180 rpm. For each transformation experiment, 1 mL of culture was centrifuged for 3 min at 11000g and resuspended in 100 μ L of the same media. The first experiment consisted on mixing 2 of these 100 μ L aliquots with 100 ng and 200 ng of *pMating221* plasmid DNA for heat shock transformation assays. Mixes were incubated on ice for 30 min, followed by 1.5 min at 42 °C and 5 min on ice; thermal shock was followed by addition of 1 mL LB media to each vial and a 1 h incubation at 37 °C, 180 rpm. Cultures were appropriately diluted in LB medium and 100 μ L were plated on kanamycin containing LB media plates (50 μ g mL⁻¹). The plates were incubated at 37 °C overnight and the resulting transform colonies were tested with Gram stain and catalase.

For the second experiment, natural transformation with no heat shock treatment was evaluated. Two of the concentrated culture aliquots of each strain were mixed with 100 ng and 300 ng of *pMating221* plasmid DNA. After 60 min of incubation at 30 °C, 1 mL of LB broth was added and incubated for 1 h at 37 °C, 180 rpm. Transformant colonies were detected in plates with LB agar kanamycin as described above. Simultaneously, both experiments were performed using *E. coli Dh5 α* as a control strain.

All the recombinant colonies obtained were cultivated in 3 consecutive rounds of growth in fresh liquid media in order to confirm the maintenance and stability of the plasmid.

3.2.4 Evaluation of *pMating221*-transformation of anaerobic isolates

Hungate tubes with 1.9 mL of pre-reduced anaerobically sterilized BHI broth media were used for anaerobiosis experiments. One colony of each isolate was resuspended in 100 μ L of peptone water and then inoculated inside the hungate tubes. After a 2-days incubation at 37 °C, cultures were centrifuged for 5 min at 5000 g and resuspended in 100 μ L of the same media. The same experiments performed for aerobic strains

were performed here. Transformant colonies were detected using BHI agar plates with kanamycin (50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) incubated under anaerobic conditions (GasPak™, H_2+CO_2) at 30 °C for 3 days.

3.2.5 *pMating221* transconjugation experiments

Pairwise of colonies mixing one Gram-positive and catalase-negative recombinant strain, with one Gram-negative and catalase-positive wild type strain as a recipient bacterium were defined to test the transfer of the conjugative plasmid *pMating221*. To perform the experiment, each colony was inoculated in 3 mL of LB broth (supplemented with kanamycin for those already transformed) and incubated overnight at 37 °C, 180 rpm. OD_{600} of cultures was measured and 1 mL of each one was adjusted to 1, followed by centrifugation at 11000 g for 5 min; the pellets were resuspended in 100 μL of LB and mixed with their corresponding partner strain. Mixtures were centrifugated at 11000 g for 5 min and resuspended in 10 μL of culture media that were droplet in LB plates and incubated overnight at 37 °C. Next day, droplets were scraped off the plate and resuspended in 1 mL of LB, dilutions were prepared and spread in plates with LB agar kanamycin and incubated overnight at 37 °C. Transformant colonies of each pairwise were differentiated with the catalase test and confirmed by Gram stain.

3.2.6 Confirmation of transformant colonies and taxonomic identification

To confirm the presence of *pMating221* in the transformant colonies, *EcFbFP* gene was amplified by PCR using 2 μL of the supernatant resulted after boil for 10 minutes each colony in 15 μL of Tris-HCl (10mM, pH 8.0), which was mixed in a 20- μL reaction of Tucantaq mix (Corpogen), containing 0.1 μM of the following pair of designed primers: E43F (5' GGAGGTTTTCTAATGG 3') and T500R (5' AAATACAGAAAAGCCC 3'). After an initial DNA denaturation step of 3 min at 95°C, the reaction mixtures were subjected to 30 cycles of 30 s at 95°C, 30 s at 55 °C, and 30 s at 72 °C.

For taxonomic assignment, 16S rRNA gene was amplified using the universal primer set 27F (5' AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG 3') and 1492R (5' TACGGYTACCTTGTTACGACTT 3') (Hongoh *et al.*, 2003) in a 50- μL reaction mixture of a high fidelity DNA polymerase (Accuzyme; Bionline). After an initial DNA denaturation step of 3 min at 95°C, the reaction mixtures were subjected to 34 cycles of 30 s at 95°C, 30 s at 58 °C, and 60 s at 72 °C. Amplicons were purified using the NucleoSpin Gel and PCR Clean-up commercial kit (Macherey-Nagel GmbH, Germany) and sequenced using Sanger platform (Macrogen, Seoul, South Korea). Sequences were cleaned and concatenated using de software UGENE (V. 34) and analyzed with the RDP classifier.

3.2.7 Design proposals of accessory modules for *pMating221* including specific genes for AMD metabolism

In previous studies (Chapter 2) we examined in detail customized AMD biochemical passive reactors, characterizing dynamics of their microbiome assemblage and their suprametabolism arrangements during continuous operation. Using shotgun metagenomics sequencing, those genes with increased frequency on intervals of efficient bioremediation were identified. As major finding, genes encoding for two-component regulatory systems, ABC transporters, sulfate and sulfite reduction, and cellulose degradation were detected with the highest increase of relative abundance.

This study is presenting three different proposals of modules including genes from ABC transporter of sulfate (Figure 2A), operon from anaerobic sulfite reductase (Figure 2B), and the β -Glucosidase enzyme (Figure 2C). In all designs, a weak constitutive promoter $PlacIQ$ (Pasotti et al., 2012) was added, together with the T7 transcriptional terminator. As shown in Figure 1, modules were designed to be introduced inside the backbone of $pMating221$ between $PacI$ and $EcoRI$ restriction sites.

First module has been designed to achieve a massive horizontal gene transfer of the sulfate transport system (Figure 2A), which has an architecture type of ATP-Binding cassette (ABC Transport) and is involved in the translocation of sulfate and thiosulfate (Davidson and Chen, 2004), crucial process during the AMD transformation. The module is ~ 7.6 Kb and is composed of 3 cistrons encoding the sulfate-binding protein (SBP) (Hryniewicz et al., 1990) and the proteins that form the channel to transport the substrate across the cytoplasmic membrane (*cysT* and *cysW*). Overlapping with *cysT*, as it was found in the metagenomics assemblage (Chapter 2), it was located the sulfur-regulated gene (*cysA*) that encodes the membrane-associated ATP-binding protein of this system (Laudenbach and Grossman, 1991). This design also includes 3 additional cistrons involved in the inorganic sulfate activation (*cysD* and *cysN*) and the APS reductase that generates sulfite production (*cysH*) (Neumann et al., 2000).

The second design consists of the anaerobic or dissimilatory sulfite reductase operon (Figure 2B), which catalyze the six-electron reduction of sulfite to sulfide (Subunit et al., 2001). This is a multisubunit enzyme and was found with a high increase of relative abundance during effective intervals of AMD bioremediation (Chapter 2). As shown in Figure 2B, the module of ~ 3.0 Kb is composed of genes encoding subunits *asrA*, *asrB* and *asrC*.

Third module is designed to spread a gene encoding the β -glucosidase, activity playing a crucial role in the enzymatic degradation of cellulose by converting cellobiose and cellodextrins to fermentable glucose (Grabnitz et al., 1991). This is a biological function of great importance inside biochemical passive reactors treating AMD since it is the main pathway to generate simple carbon sources. Construct of ~2.5 Kb includes a single gene for the β -glucosidase expression (Figure 2C).

The complete modules with the same nucleotide sequences on inferred assemblies with the annotated gene from metagenomic contigs of higher read coverage (frequency) were subjected to two independent chemical gene synthesis trials by the companies Genewiz (New Jersey, USA) and ABM Good (Richmond, Canada). Otherwise, detection of PCR gene fragments amplified from the original metagenomic DNA shotgun sequenced with primers targeting these genes was performed.

Figure 2. Structure of accessory modules designed to introduce them inside *pMating221* and spread metabolic functions specially related to AMD bioremediation: 2A. Sulfate transport system; 2B. anaerobic sulfite reduction; and 2C. β -Glucosidase activity.

3.3 Results and Discussion

Genetic bioaugmentation has been since long time ago under study as an awaited strategy to improve bioremediation. The knowledge generated to date by synthetic biology has allowed the development of stable engineering strains and several genetic tools that could be easily mobilized in multiple hosts (Czamanski *et al.*, 2019). The construction of vectors based on a modular architecture to fine tune spread, expression, activity or containment has accelerated the development of novel toolkits of genetic parts, expanding the possibilities for biotechnology. In this study, plasticity and wide host range of *pMating221* was demonstrated, confirming it as an excellent tool for foreseen genetic bioaugmentation applications of environmental microbiomes.

A total of 45 strains with several types of morphologies were isolated from AMD water and highly impacted soils; among these, 14 were obtained under anaerobic conditions. The colonies were also cultured on plates supplemented with kanamycin ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) to test natural resistance, and 10 of them with natural antibiotic resistance were discarded for further experiments. This also means wild types of bacterial strains having incompatible plasmids would be refractory to the additional genetic transformation with this plasmid. At the end, promiscuity of plasmid *pMating221* was tested using 35 different strains from the genera *Aeromonas*, *Bacillus* and *Cellulosimicrobium* (Figure 3), a selection of Gram-positive, Gram-negative, aerobic, and facultative anaerobic bacteria remarking the wide taxonomic range of acquisition and transfer of the plasmid and the main selective function encoded.

One of the main features of the plasmid *pMating221* is the presence of the RK2 origin of replication, which provides the vector with the ability to replicate and maintain itself in almost all Gram-negative bacteria (Fang and Helinski, 1991) and in Gram-positive bacteria as well (Yokoi *et al.*, 2019). Our results demonstrated that *pMating221* has indeed a broad host range of transformation and replication in this test of environmental bacterial strains with distant phylogenetic relationship. After heat shock treatment all colonies were able to successfully take up the plasmid from the media achieving massive growth in plates supplemented with kanamycin. Comparing the results according to the initial plasmid concentration, in all cases the number of transformant colonies was up to 100X higher using 100 ng of plasmid DNA (Table 1); 89% of the isolates, including Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria showed to be natural competent cell acquiring external

Table 1. Characterization of isolates and the results of the transformation experiments.

Strain Code	Gram	Catalase	Taxonomy	Heat Shock (100ng)	Heat Shock (300ng)	No Heat Shock (100 ng)
An10	BG+	-	Bacillus sp.	5.60E+03	2.90E+01	5.60E+02
An18	BG+	-	Bacillus sp.	6.50E+03	4.50E+01	3.70E+02
KA4	BG+	-	Bacillus sp.	9.90E+03	6.30E+01	4.50E+02
KB1	BG+	-	Bacillus sp.	7.80E+03	1.80E+01	8.70E+02
An11	BG+	-	Bacillus sp.	2.10E+03	1.40E+01	4.70E+02
An9	BG+	-	Bacillus sp.	6.30E+03	2.60E+01	9.60E+02
KC2	BG+	+	Cellulosimicrobium sp.	1.20E+02	1.20E+02	5.90E+01
47	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	8.60E+04	3.60E+02	6.30E+03
10	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	5.60E+04	9.60E+02	4.50E+03
l1	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	6.30E+05	7.80E+03	3.20E+03
18	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	2.80E+05	9.80E+03	9.60E+03
34	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	7.50E+04	2.90E+02	3.10E+03
l4	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	8.70E+04	3.10E+02	9.20E+03
KA3	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	4.50E+02	1.60E+01	0.00
11	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	7.80E+04	6.30E+02	3.60E+03
31	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	3.90E+04	8.50E+02	7.30E+03
6	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	3.60E+04	4.50E+02	6.30E+03
An1	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	8.90E+03	3.20E+01	3.20E+02
L2	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	6.90E+04	1.20E+02	6.10E+03
An12	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	3.60E+02	1.10E+01	0.00
L27	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	7.80E+04	1.30E+02	8.50E+03
An3	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	4.80E+03	1.90E+01	0.00
L26	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	9.50E+04	3.20E+02	8.30E+03
An4	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	5.30E+03	6.90E+01	3.10E+02
46	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	8.20E+04	5.60E+02	8.90E+03
l2	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	7.90E+04	3.60E+02	9.80E+03
22	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	4.80E+04	4.70E+02	7.80E+03
An13	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	8.90E+03	2.30E+01	9.60E+02
D43	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	7.80E+04	4.90E+02	5.80E+03
D42	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	9.10E+04	9.80E+02	7.80E+03
9.1	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	9.80E+04	5.90E+02	8.90E+03
4	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	1.70E+04	6.70E+02	9.80E+03
KA	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	9.80E+03	9.30E+01	0.00
D41	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	9.80E+04	7.80E+02	9.80E+03
3	BG-	+	Aeromonas sp.	2.50E+04	8.90E+02	1.70E+03

Horizontal gene transfer mediated by plasmids has been considered as one of the major mechanisms for the bacterial adaptation to environmental challenges, and therefore also represents additional costs for the host. The acquisition of a plasmid implies an additional physiological load in replication of the episomal element

and in the production of the plasmid encoded proteins, the expression of new metabolic capabilities, and the production of conjugative pili (Bellanger et al., 2014); consequently, in the absence of a positive selection, plasmids maintained in the population are predicted to be lost due to the selective advantage of strains without it, or prone to mutant selection mainly due to genetic drift. After transformation, the original pigmentation of all colonies, turned them to a light-bright color with green hints (Figure 4), however the fluorescence emitted by them was much lower than the one by the control strain. This can be explained by copy number, transcriptional and translational constrains, or by the energy required by the new host for the plasmid adaptation. The control strain DH5 α may have a better energetic efficiency and redox homeostasis within the cell, reflected on the difference in fluorescence intensity (Nikel and de Lorenzo, 2013).

Figure 4. Photographs showing how *pMating221* acquisition changed the original pigmentation of the colony code 22 (*Aeromonas* sp.). A. Original pigmentation of the colony; B. Morphology acquired after transformation.

Table 2. Pairwise of colonies tested in transconjugation experiments

Strain 1	Strain 2	Result
An10	KA3	+
	4	+
An18	An12	+
	6	+
KA4	An3	+
	D41	+
KB1	KA	+
	4	+
An11	34	+
	11	+
An9	L2	+
	L26	+

The accessory gene modules that were detected by shotgun metagenomics as encoding selected metabolic activities on efficient AMD bioremediation steps were partially chemically synthesized in fragments, however, astonishingly, in all the trials for the final assembly, it was never resulting in the exact coding frame in the final recombinant strain with such construct. Specifically, the final product of the complete module synthesis containing the sulfate transport system inhibited growth of the *E. coli* host competent cells (Dh5 α /JM110/EPI400), suggesting this construct has a deleterious or toxic effect, exerting a high physiological load. For the other two modules, unique single random insertions were detected in the final complete modules, resulting in a pseudogene construct with a truncated putative protein product when cloned in pUC57. Those designs in the clones for these modules presented discrepancies in their sequence, which could be compensatory mutations (Bellanger et al., 2014) given the presence of antibiotic as a positive selection strong enough for the bacteria to express the plasmid, but the synthesis of no vital accessory enzymes with non-functional modifications could mean energy advantages, or the toxic effect of the complete module, so only mutated versions can be maintained in the recombinant strains.

Yet demonstrated the transformation and conjugal properties of *pMating221*, it is required the study of its dissemination inside a complex microbial community; however, as it is well known that culturable fraction of bacteria is often <1 %, it is necessary to implement culture-independent strategies to estimate the plasmid uptake and transfer across various taxa. Further experiments require the combination of omic technologies

and microcosms set-up to analyze microbial community structure before and after the plasmid dissemination.

3.4 Conclusions

Our results demonstrated that pMating221 has a broad-host range, it worked under aerobic and anaerobic conditions, and it is an ideal vector to generate massive horizontal gene transfer. Its modular architecture allows easy insertion of specific genes making it an effective tool for spreading key functions inside a microbial community. The accessory modules that were designed for metabolic activities related to AMD metabolism were not able to be cloned, therefore further work is required to validate why these sequences were not viable for the cells. As a final outlook of this work, the pMating221 tested shows a promising feature and could serve as a cornerstone for further extended trials on gene bioaugmentations of environmental microbiomes aiming improved bioremediation processes.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the financial support from Departamento Administrativo de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación – COLCIENCIAS – through doctoral fellowship “Beca de Estudios Doctorales Nacionales 727 granted to M. Villegas-Plazas and the access to laboratory infrastructure kindly provided by Prof Fabio Roldán, Ph.D. USBA-PUJ.

3.5 References

- Akcil, A. and Koldas, S. (2006) Acid Mine Drainage (AMD): causes , treatment and case studies. 14: 1139–1145.
- Bathe, S., Mohan, T.V.K., Wuertz, S., and Hausner, M. (2004) Bioaugmentation of a sequencing batch biofilm reactor by horizontal gene transfer. *Water Sci Technol* 49: 337–44.
- Bellanger, X., Guilloteau, H., Bonot, S., and Merlin, C. (2014) Demonstrating plasmid-based horizontal gene transfer in complex environmental matrices: A practical approach for a critical review. *Sci Total Environ* 493: 872–882.
- Courvalin, P. (1994) Transfer of Antibiotic Resistance Genes between Gram-Positive and Gram-Negative Bacteria. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 38: 1447–1451.
- Czamanski, L., Westmann, C., Guazzaroni, M.-E., Siddaiah, C., Gupta, V., and Silva-Rocha, R. (2019) Recent advances in plasmid-based tools for establishing novel microbial chassis. *Biotechnol Adv* 107433.
- Davidson, A.L. and Chen, J. (2004) ATP-Binding Cassette Transporters in Bacteria. *Annu Rev Biochem* 73: 241–268.
- Drepper, T., Eggert, T., Circolone, F., Heck, A., Krauß, U., Guterl, J.K., et al. (2007) Reporter proteins for in vivo fluorescence without oxygen. *Nat Biotechnol* 25: 443–445.
- Fang, F.C. and Helinski, D.R. (1991) Broad-host-range properties of plasmid RK2: Importance of overlapping genes encoding the plasmid replication initiation protein TrfA. *J Bacteriol* 173: 5861–5868.
- Garbisu, C., Garaiyurrebaso, O., Epelde, L., and Grohmann, E. (2017) Plasmid-Mediated Bioaugmentation for the Bioremediation of Contaminated Soils. 8: 1–13.
- Grabnitz, F., Seiss, M., Rucknagel, K.P., and Staudenbauer, W.L. (1991) Structure of the B-glucosidase gene bglA of *Clostridium thermocellum*. *Eur J Biochem* 309: 301–309.
- Harrison, E. and Brockhurst, M.A. (2012) Plasmid-mediated horizontal gene transfer is a coevolutionary process. *Trends Microbiol* 20: 262–267.
- Hays, S.G., Patrick, W.G., Ziesack, M., Oxman, N., and Silver, P.A. (2015) Better together: Engineering and application of microbial symbioses. *Curr Opin Biotechnol* 36: 40–49.
- Hongoh, Y., Yuzawa, H., Ohkuma, M., and Kudo, T. (2003) Evaluation of primers and PCR conditions for the analysis of 16S rRNA genes from a natural environment. *FEMS Microbiol Lett* 221: 299–304.

- Hryniewicz, M., Sirko, A., Palucha, A., Bock, A., and Hulanicka, D. (1990) Sulfate and thiosulfate transport in *Escherichia coli* K-12: Identification of a gene encoding a novel protein involved in thiosulfate binding. *J Bacteriol* 172: 3358–3366.
- Landrigan, P.J., Fuller, R., Acosta, N.J.R., Adeyi, O., Arnold, R., Basu, N. (Nil), et al. (2018) The Lancet Commission on pollution and health. *Lancet* 391: 462–512.
- Laudenbach, D.E. and Grossman, A.R. (1991) Characterization and mutagenesis of sulfur-regulated genes in a cyanobacterium: Evidence for function in sulfate transport. *J Bacteriol* 173: 2739–2750.
- Martínez-García, E., Aparicio, T., de Lorenzo, V., and Nikel, P.I. (2014) New transposon tools tailored for metabolic engineering of Gram-negative microbial cell factories. *Front Bioeng Biotechnol* 2: 1–13.
- Neumann, S., Wynen, A., Trüper, H.G., and Dahl, C. (2000) Characterization of the *cys* gene locus from *Allochromatium vinosum* indicates an unusual sulfate assimilation pathway. *Mol Biol Rep* 27: 27–33.
- Nikel, P.I. and de Lorenzo, V. (2013) Engineering an anaerobic metabolic regime in *Pseudomonas putida* KT2440 for the anoxic biodegradation of 1,3-dichloroprop-1-ene. *Metab Eng* 15: 98–112.
- Nordstrom, D.K. (2019) Geochemical modelling for mine site characterization and remediation. *E3S Web Conf* 98: 4–8.
- Pasotti, L., Politi, N., Zucca, S., Cusella de Angelis, M.G., and Magni, P. (2012) Bottom-up engineering of biological systems through standard bricks: A modularity study on basic parts and devices. *PLoS One* 7: 1–10.
- Pinilla-redondo, R., Cyriaque, V., Jacquiod, S., Sørensen, S.J., and Riber, L. (2018) Monitoring plasmid-mediated horizontal gene transfer in microbiomes: recent advances and future perspectives. *Plasmid* 99: 56–67.
- Springael, D. and Top, E.M. (2004) Horizontal gene transfer and microbial adaptation to xenobiotics: new types of mobile genetic elements and lessons from ecological studies. *Trends Microbiol* 12: 53–58.
- Subunit, D., Laue, H., Friedrich, M., Ruff, J., and Alasdair, M. (2001) Dissimilatory Sulfite Reductase (Desulfoviridin) of the Taurine-Degrading , Non-Sulfate-Reducing Bacterium *Bilophila wadsworthia* RZATAU Contains a Fused Dissimilatory Sulfite Reductase (Desulfoviridin) of the Taurine-Degrading , Non-Sulfate-Reducing B.
- Tielker, D., Eichhof, I., Jaeger, K.E., and Ernst, J.F. (2009) Flavin mononucleotide-based fluorescent protein as an oxygen-independent reporter in *Candida albicans* and *saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Eukaryot Cell* 8: 913–915.
- Yokoi, T., Itaya, M., Mori, H., Kataoka, M., 2019. Optimization of RK2-based gene introduction system for *Bacillus subtilis*. *J. Gen. Appl. Microbiol.* 65, 265–272. <https://doi.org/10.2323/jgam.2018.11.005>
- Zhang, Q., Wang, B., Cao, Z., and Yu, Y. (2012) Plasmid-mediated bioaugmentation for the degradation of chlorpyrifos in soil. *J Hazard Mater* 221–222: 178–184.
- Zobel, S., Benedetti, I., Eisenbach, L., De Lorenzo, V., Wierckx, N., and Blank, L.M. (2015) Tn7-Based Device for Calibrated Heterologous Gene Expression in *Pseudomonas putida*. *ACS Synth Biol* 4: 1341–1351.

Outlook and Final Considerations

Marcela Villegas-Plazas^{1,2}

¹RG Microbial Ecology: Metabolism, Genomics & Evolution, Div. Ecogenomics & Holobionts, Microbiomas Foundation, LT11A, 250008, Chia, Colombia

²Environmental Microbiology and Biotechnology Laboratory, Engineering School of Environmental & Natural Resources, Engineering Faculty, Universidad del Valle, Cali, Colombia

1.1 Concluding remarks

Coal mining-industry plays an important role in the economic development of many countries but produces highly significant alterations on the environment, mainly due to the generation of acid mine drainage (AMD) (Akcil and Koldas, 2006; Nordstrom, 2019). This is a strong acidic metal-rich wastewater that has serious impact on human health and ecosystems (Landrigan et al., 2018), and its treatment has become an environmental priority challenge (Jennings et al., 2008). Despite there have been multiple physic-chemical treatments widely used to cope with this issue (Genty et al., 2018), bioremediation has emerged as a sustainable and safer alternative (Johnson and Hallberg, 2005; Fitch, 2015); during the last 5 years, great progresses in its implementation have been reported.

Bibliometric analysis representing the structure of research topics in the field of AMD bioremediation during the last decade (Figure 1), has evidenced how metagenomics approaches and microbial ecology studies from AMD ecosystems have preceded the development of efficient bioremediation systems such as biochemical passive reactors (BPR). These exploratory investigations have directed the efforts to a new integrated perspective of bioremediation, which backs up the transition between the use of unique strains to the use of complex microbial communities. Following the same trend, this thesis has provided metagenomic insights inferring microbial dynamics into those engineering ecosystems as a necessary insight to develop improvement strategies for them. Our proposal is a reminding that descriptive observations play a vital role in scientific progress, building the foundation for the applied sciences that follows. I presented a broad overview of microbiomes architecture under AMD selective pressure, including composition, networks of microbial taxa, functional potential and gene abundance, which provided hints about the requirements of microbial communities to achieve an effective AMD bioremediation. Based on that characterization, we proposed the design of a bioremediation improving strategy using genetic bioaugmentation.

The extreme conditions of AMD water make it inhabited by microbial communities of low diversity predominated by acidophilic sulfur and/or iron-oxidizers bacteria (Chapter 1). The contrast of their composition with that from AMD impacted environments and bioremediation systems, showed that despite the acidity and high concentration of sulfate and heavy metals, there was a functional acclimatization after AMD perturbation, followed by the establishment of highly diversity communities predominated by sulfate reducer bacteria and sugar fermenters groups (Chapter 1 and 2). This thesis identified that the diversity of microbiomes from BPRs increased with AMD exposure time, evidencing that the presence of the pollutant led to the growth of specialized species, mainly those from the phyla Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes and Proteobacteria (Chapter 2). The accumulation of these phyla have been considered an indicator of stable operation in AMD bioremediation (Aoyagi et al., 2017) because their co-occurrence represents the ecological

Transformation and transconjugation properties of *pMating221* have been tested using single strains, but now it would be necessary to scale-up the experiments to microcosms of complex microbial communities that resemble the conditions of the BPRs. The first trial would be done by using the same reactive mixture from the reactors (described in Chapter 2), adding antibiotic (Km) and introducing the vector *pMating221* with kanamycin resistance as a selective marker. The plasmid would be introduced in both ways, as free DNA in the environment and inside a donor bacteria (those that were isolated from AMD impacted soils in chapter 3), and its dissemination would be determined by comparing the shifts of microbial community structure using 16S-target sequencing. Simultaneously, modules to introduce specific genes to the vector must be redesigned, so they can be cloned and provide metabolic properties to the host cell. The new vectors will have to be also evaluated using single strains and microcosms, but under specific selective pressures, such as high concentrations of sulfate or cellulose as a unique carbon source; the antibiotic resistance would be deleted before implementing a possible genetic bioaugmentation strategy inside BPRs or AMD ecosystems.

Although much work is still required to effectively develop a genetic bioaugmentation strategy that improves AMD bioremediation inside biochemical passive reactors, and it has been a topic of investigation and debate over the last 40 years, in this work it is the first time it is ever considered specifically for AMD bioremediation, the results obtained from this thesis are providing a sound foundation for its further trial and implementation. We are providing novel information and insights about the shifts and dynamics of microbial communities during the AMD treatment, unraveling co-selected functions that are key in their adaptation process, and identifying those that could be the ultimate target for genetic bioaugmentation strategies. Also, as a gene mobilization tool, an initial test of conjugative properties of plasmid *pMating221* has been advanced. Finally, an additional contribution of this doctoral thesis is the concept in which systems biology and synthetic biology can be intertwined to address in a comprehensive way the bioremediation strategies.

1.2 References

- Akcil, A. and Koldas, S. (2006) Acid Mine Drainage (AMD): causes , treatment and case studies. **14**: 1139–1145.
- Aoyagi, T., Hamai, T., Hori, T., Sato, Yuki, Kobayashi, M., Sato, Yuya, et al. (2017) Hydraulic retention time and pH affect the performance and microbial communities of passive bioreactors for treatment of acid mine drainage. *AMB Express* **7**: 1–11.
- Fitch, M. (2015) Mine-Impacted Water and Biochemical Reactors, Elsevier Inc.
- Genty, T., Bussière, B., Benzaazoua, M., Neculita, C.M., and Zagury, G.J. (2018) Iron removal in highly contaminated acid mine drainage using passive biochemical reactors. 1833–1843.
- Jennings, S.R., Blicher, S., Neuman, P., and Dennis, R. (2008) Acid mine drainage and effects on fish health and ecology: a review. *Reclam Res Gr* **1**: 1–26.
- Johnson, D.B. and Hallberg, K.B. (2005) Acid mine drainage remediation options: A review. *Sci Total Environ* **338**: 3–14.
- Landrigan, P.J., Fuller, R., Acosta, N.J.R., Adeyi, O., Arnold, R., Basu, N. (Nil), et al. (2018) The Lancet Commission on pollution and health. *Lancet* **391**: 462–512.
- Nordstrom, D.K. (2019) Geochemical modelling for mine site characterization and remediation. *E3S Web Conf* **98**: 4–8.

2.1 Annex Chapter I

Supplementary Material

Methodology

Bioinformatics analyses were performed using QIIME 1.9.1 (Kuczynski *et al.*, 2011). Chimeric sequences were identified, extracted and excluded out of the datasets by Usearch 6.1 and a multi-step closed-reference OTU picking workflow was performed within the QIIME system. Using this methodology, OTUs were picked assigning the reads to species groups based on 97% sequence similarity. Taxonomic assignment was performed using SILVA core database (132 released, April 2018) and alpha and beta diversity analysis were performed with both platforms QIIME and Phyloseq R package (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013).

Open-source R package Tax4Fun (Aßhauer *et al.*, 2015) was used to predict the functional capabilities of microbial communities, as a reported proxy estimate of functional profiles inferred from 16S amplicon sequences in good agreement with functional profiles inferred from metagenomic shotgun sequencing from the same samples (Kaiser *et al.*, 2016; Kavamura *et al.*, 2018). First, it was necessary to construct an OTU table in biom format using the database SILVA 123, this was achieved using the same methodology in QIIME 1.9.1 described above. The Tax4Fun function was run with all default settings. The table with 16S rRNA gene-predicted functions was exported into Excel spreadsheets for subsequent statistical analyses. All statistical analyses presented here were performed using default R packages.

Supplementary Table 1. List of most representative studies that have investigated AMD microbial communities using high-throughput sequencing technologies and omics approaches.

	Location	Habitat	'omic' approach	Year	Ref
*1	USA	Water Sediments	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2017	(Havig <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
2	California, USA	Surface of a slowly draining	Complete genome reconstruction from uncultivated microorganisms.	2013	(Yelton <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
3	Jiangxi, China	AMD water and leaching heap	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2013	(Hu <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
4	California, USA	Floating biofilms in AMD water	Proteomics	2011	(Mueller <i>et al.</i> , 2011)
5	Asturias, Spain	AMD water	16S and 18S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2017	(Mesa <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
6	Huaxi, China	Water and sediments AMD impacted	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2016	(Sun <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
*7	Southwest, China	Sediments from AMD watershed.	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2015	(W. Sun <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
8	Northern Sweden	Biofilm from a stream flowing along a tunnel.	Functional metagenomics	2015	(Liljeqvist <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
*9	Balaghat, India	Tailing sediment	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2017	(Gupta <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
*10	Guiyang, China	Soil AMD-impacted	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2014	(M. Sun <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
11	Afon Goch river	Water and sediments AMD impacted.	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2018	(Aguinaga <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
12	Guangdong Providence, China	AMD water	Functional metagenomics and Metatranscriptomics	2015	(Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
13	Transbaikal region, Russia	AMD water	Complete genome reconstruction from uncultivated microorganisms.	2015	(V. V. Kadnikov <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
14	Guangdong Province, China	AMD water	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2017	(Liang <i>et al.</i> , 2018)

15	South Africa	Bioreactor of mine effluent treatment	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2017	(Grewar <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
16	Butler Country, USA	AMD-impacted soil in 1950 amended with different organic material	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2015	(Hillwig <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
17	Ontario, Canada	AMD water	16S and 18S rRNA targeted- sequencing.	2017	(Auld <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
18	Guangdong Province, China	Tailing	16S and 18S rRNA targeted- sequencing and functional metagenomics.	2013	(Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
19	Anhui Province, China	Tailing	16S and 18S rRNA targeted- sequencing.	2014	(Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
20	California, USA	Biofilm from AMD water	Metatranscriptomics	2015	(Goltsman <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
*21	Copper Cliffs, Canada	AMD water	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2013	(Auld <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
22	Mpumalanga Providence, South Africa	Biofilm from AMD water	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2010	(Fosso-Kankeu and Redelinghuys, 2010)
23	Guangdong Province, China	Soil from rice paddies impacted with AMD	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2018	(Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
24	Guangdong Province, China	AMD-impacted soil	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2016	(Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
*25	Mpumalanga Providence, South Africa	AMD water	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2014	(Keshri <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
26	Lusatia, Germany	Enrichment culture from AMD water	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing and functional metagenomics.	2016	(Mühling <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
27	Mpumalanga Providence, South Africa	AMD water	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2016	(de Klerk <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
28	Shanxi, China	Sludge from secondary sedimentation tanks	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2014	(Ma <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
29	Japan	Sulfate-reducing bioreactor	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2017	(Aoyagi <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
*30	Cundinamarca, Colombia	Biochemical Reactors Passive	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2018	(Vasquez <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
*31	Anhui Providence, China	AMD water	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2017	(Hao <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
32	Sherlovaya, Russia	AMD water	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2016	(V. V Kadnikov <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
*33	North Lima	AMD-impacted soil	16S rRNA targeted- sequencing	2014	(Brantner and Senko, 2014)

* The asterisk indicates the studies comparatively reanalyzed in this review.

Supplementary Table 2. GenBank accession number and references of compiled data used in this study

Accession Number	Type of Sample	Reference
SRX1943889	AMD Biofilm	(Havig <i>et al.</i> 2017)
SRX1943888	AMD Biofilm	(Havig <i>et al.</i> 2017)
SRX1943887	AMD Biofilm	(Havig <i>et al.</i> 2017)
SRX1943886	AMD Biofilm	(Havig <i>et al.</i> 2017)
SRX1943885	AMD Biofilm	(Havig <i>et al.</i> 2017)
SRX1943884	AMD Biofilm	(Havig <i>et al.</i> 2017)
SRX1943883	AMD Biofilm	(Havig <i>et al.</i> 2017)

SRX1943882	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943881	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943880	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943879	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943878	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943877	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943876	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943875	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943874	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943873	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943872	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943871	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943870	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943869	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRX1943868	AMD Biofilm	(Havig et al. 2017)
SRR1518383	AMD-impacted environment	(Sun et al. 2015b)
SRX2512346	AMD-impacted environment	(Gupta et al. 2017)
SRX2512345	AMD-impacted environment	(Gupta et al. 2017)
SRX2512227	AMD-impacted environment	(Gupta et al. 2017)
SRX726585	AMD-impacted environment	(Sun et al. 2015a)
SRX726584	AMD-impacted environment	(Sun et al. 2015a)
SRX726583	AMD-impacted environment	(Sun et al. 2015a)
SRX726580	AMD-impacted environment	(Sun et al. 2015a)
SRX700717	AMD-impacted environment	(Sun et al. 2015a)
SRR801098	AMD Water	(Auld et al. 2013)
SRR1584394	AMD Water	(Keshri et al. 2015)
SRR4045549	AMD Water	(Hao et al. 2017)
SRR1207206	AMD-impacted environment	(Brantner and Senko 2014)
PRJNA532628	Biochemical Passive reactor	(Vasquez et al. 2018)

References

- Aguinaga, O.E., McMahon, A., White, K.N., Dean, A.P., Pittman, J.K., and Dean, A.P. (2018) Microbial Community Shifts in Response to Acid Mine Drainage Pollution Within a Natural Wetland Ecosystem. *Front Microbiol* **9**: 1–14.
- Aoyagi, T., Hamai, T., Hori, T., Sato, Yuki, Kobayashi, M., Sato, Yuya, et al. (2017) Hydraulic retention time and pH affect the performance and microbial communities of passive bioreactors for treatment of acid mine drainage. *AMB Express* **7**: 1–11.
- Aßhauer, K.P., Wemheuer, B., Daniel, R., and Meinicke, P. (2015) Tax4Fun: Predicting functional profiles from metagenomic 16S rRNA data. *Bioinformatics* **31**: 2882–2884.
- Auld, R.R., Mykytczuk, N.C.S., Leduc, L.G., and Merritt, T.J.S. (2017) Seasonal Variation in an Acid Mine Drainage Microbial Community. *Can J Microbiol* **63**: 137–152.
- Auld, R.R., Myre, M., Mykytczuk, N.C.S., Leduc, L.G., and Merritt, T.J.S. (2013) Characterization of the microbial acid mine drainage microbial community using culturing and direct sequencing techniques. *J Microbiol Methods* **93**: 108–115.
- Brantner, J.S. and Senko, J.M. (2014) Response of soil-associated microbial communities to intrusion of coal mine-derived acid mine drainage. *Environ Sci Technol* **48**: 8556–8563.
- Chen, L.-X., Hu, M., Huang, L.-N., Hua, Z.-S., Kuang, J.-L., Li, S.-J., and Shu, W.-S. (2014) Comparative metagenomic and metatranscriptomic analyses of microbial communities in acid mine drainage. *ISME J* **9**: 1579–1592.

- Chen, L. xing, Li, J. tian, Chen, Y. ting, Huang, L. nan, Hua, Z. shuang, Hu, M., and Shu, W. sheng (2013) Shifts in microbial community composition and function in the acidification of a lead/zinc mine tailings. *Environ Microbiol* **15**: 2431–2444.
- Fosso-Kankeu, E. and Redelinguys, J. (2010) Bacterial ecology of bio lms sustaining pollution by acid mine drainage near mining areas in Mpumalanga Province – South Africa. In, *MWD Conference.*, pp. 332–338.
- Goltsman, D.S.A., Comolli, L.R., Thomas, B.C., and Banfield, J.F. (2015) Community transcriptomics reveals unexpected high microbial diversity in acidophilic biofilm communities. *ISME J* **9**: 1014–1023.
- Grewar, T., Effluent, L., Salo, M., Bomberg, M., Grewar, T., and Seepei, L. (2017) Compositions of the Microbial Consortia Present in eduction Processes During Mine Effluent Treatment Biological Sulphate Reduction Processes During Mine. 14–21.
- Gupta, A., Dutta, A., Sarkar, J., Paul, D., Panigrahi, M.K., and Sar, P. (2017) Metagenomic exploration of microbial community in mine tailings of Malanjhand copper project, India. *Genomics Data*.
- Hao, C., Wei, P., Pei, L., Du, Z., Zhang, Y., and Lu, Y. (2017) Significant seasonal variations of microbial community in an acid mine drainage lake in Anhui Province , China. *Environ Pollut* 1–10.
- Havig, J.R., Grettenberger, C., and Hamilton, T.L. (2017) Geochemistry and microbial community composition across a range of acid mine drainage impact and implications for the Neoproterozoic-Paleoproterozoic transition. *J Geophys Res Biogeosciences* **122**: 1404–1422.
- Hillwig, M., Scheunemann, D., Clark, S., and Kalevitch, M. (2015) Comparison of bacterial DNA from soil contaminated by Acid Mine Drainage and amended sites of Butler County in Western Pennsylvania, USA. *Can J Pure Appl Sci* **9**: 3339–3343.
- Hu, Q., Liang, Y.L., Yin, H.Q., Guo, X., Hao, X.D., Liu, X.D., and Qiu, G.Z. (2013) Metagenomic Insights into the Microbial Community Diversity between Leaching Heap and Acid Mine Drainage. *Adv Mater Res* **825**: 141–144.
- Kadnikov, V. V., Ivashenko, D.A., Beletskii, A. V., Mardanov, A. V., Danilova, E. V., Pimenov, N. V., et al. (2016) A novel uncultured bacterium of the family Gallionellaceae: Description and genome reconstruction based on metagenomic analysis of microbial community in acid mine drainage. *Microbiology* **85**: 449–461.
- Kadnikov, V. V., Ivashenko, D.A., Beletsky, A. V., Mardanov, A. V., Danilova, E. V., and Pimenov, N. V. (2016) Effect of Metal Concentration on the Microbial Community in Acid Mine Drainage of a Polysulfide Ore Deposit. *Mikrobiologiya* **85**: 745–751.
- Kaiser, K., Wemheuer, B., Korolkow, V., Wemheuer, F., Nacke, H., Schöning, I., et al. (2016) Driving forces of soil bacterial community structure, diversity, and function in temperate grasslands and forests. *Sci Rep* **6**: 1–12.
- Kavamura, V.N., Hayat, R., Clark, I.M., Rossmann, M., Mendes, R., Hirsch, P.R., and Mauchline, T.H. (2018) Inorganic nitrogen application affects both taxonomical and predicted functional structure of wheat rhizosphere bacterial communities. *Front Microbiol* **9**: 1–15.
- Keshri, J., Mankazana, B.B.J., and Momba, M.N.B. (2015) Profile of bacterial communities in South African mine-water samples using Illumina next-generation sequencing platform. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* **99**: 3233–3242.
- de Klerk, A.R., Oberholster, P.J., van Wyk, J.H., Truter, J.C., Schaefer, L.M., and Botha, A.M. (2016) The effect of rehabilitation measures on ecological infrastructure in response to acid mine drainage from coal mining. *Ecol Eng* **95**: 463–474.
- Kuczynski, J., Stombaugh, J., Walters, W.A., González, A., Caporaso, J.G., and Knight, R. (2011) Using QIIME to analyze 16S rRNA gene sequences from microbial communities. *Curr Protoc Bioinformatics* **Chapter 10**: Unit 10.7.
- Liang, J., Li, X., Shu, H., Wang, P., Kuang, J., Liu, J., et al. (2018) Fine-scale spatial patterns in microbial community composition in an acid mine drainage. 1–8.
- Liljeqvist, M., Ossandon, F.J., Gonz, C., Rajan, S., Stell, A., Valdes, J., et al. (2015) Metagenomic analysis reveals adaptations to a cold-adapted lifestyle in a low-temperature. 1–12.
- Liu, J., Hua, Z.S., Chen, L.X., Kuang, J.L., Li, S.J., Shu, W.S., and Huang, L.N. (2014) Correlating microbial diversity patterns with geochemistry in an extreme and heterogeneous environment of mine tailings. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **80**: 3677–3686.
- Ma, Q., Qu, Y.Y., Zhang, X.W., Shen, W.L., Liu, Z.Y., Wang, J.W., et al. (2015) Identification of the microbial community composition and structure of coal-mine wastewater treatment plants. *Microbiol Res* **175**: 1–5.
- McMurdie, P.J. and Holmes, S. (2013) phyloseq: an R package for reproducible interactive analysis and graphics of microbiome census data. *PLoS One* **8**: 1–11.
- Mesa, V., Gallego, J.L.R., González-gil, R., Lauga, B., Sánchez, J., Méndez-garcía, C., and Peláez, A.I. (2017) Bacterial, Archaeal, and Eukaryotic Diversity across Distinct Microhabitats in an Acid Mine Drainage. *Front Microbiol* **8**: 1–17.
- Mueller, R.S., Dill, B.D., Pan, C., Belnap, C.P., Thomas, B.C., Verberkmoes, N.C., et al. (2011) Proteome changes in the initial bacterial colonist during ecological succession in an acid mine drainage biofilm community. *Environ Microbiol* **13**: 2279–2292.

- Mühling, M., Poehlein, A., Stuhr, A., Voitel, M., Daniel, R., and Schlömann, M. (2016) Reconstruction of the metabolic potential of acidophilic sideroxydans strains from the metagenome of an microaerophilic enrichment culture of acidophilic iron-oxidizing bacteria from a pilot plant for the treatment of acid mine drainage reveals metabolic . *Front Microbiol* **7**: 1–16.
- Sun, M., Xiao, T., Ning, Z., and Xiao, E. (2015) Microbial community analysis in rice paddy soils irrigated by acid mine drainage contaminated water. 2911–2922.
- Sun, W., Xiao, E., Krumins, V., Dong, Y., and Xiao, T. (2016) Characterization of the microbial community composition and the distribution of Fe-metabolizing bacteria in a creek contaminated by acid mine drainage. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol*.
- Sun, W., Xiao, T., Sun, M., Dong, Y., Ning, Z., Xiao, E., et al. (2015) Diversity of the Sediment Microbial Community in the Aha Watershed (Southwest China) in Response to Acid Mine Drainage. **81**: 4874–4884.
- Vasquez, Y., Escobar, M.C., Saenz, J.S., Quiceno-Vallejo, M.F., Neculita, C.M., Arbeli, Z., and Roldan, F. (2018) Effect of hydraulic retention time on microbial community in biochemical passive reactors during treatment of acid mine drainage. *Bioresour Technol* **247**: 624–632.
- Wang, H., Guo, C.L., Yang, C.F., Lu, G.N., Chen, M.Q., and Dang, Z. (2016) Distribution and diversity of bacterial communities and sulphate-reducing bacteria in a paddy soil irrigated with acid mine drainage. *J Appl Microbiol* **121**: 196–206.
- Wang, H., Zeng, Y., Guo, C., Bao, Y., Lu, G., Reinfelder, J.R., and Dang, Z. (2018) Bacterial, archaeal, and fungal community responses to acid mine drainage-laden pollution in a rice paddy soil ecosystem. *Sci Total Environ* **616–617**: 107–116.
- Yelton, A.P., Comolli, L.R., Justice, N.B., Castelle, C., Deneff, V.J., Thomas, B.C., and Banfield, J.F. (2013) Comparative genomics in acid mine drainage biofilm communities reveals metabolic and structural differentiation of co-occurring archaea. *BMC Genomics* **14**.

2.2 Annex Chapter II

Supplementary online material

Chapter II, Supplementary Figure 1. Relative frequencies of phyla in each sample.

Chapter II Supplementary Table 3 is available in the Open Data source repository Zenodo URL: [10.5281/zenodo.3787952](https://zenodo.org/record/3787952)